

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

D.4.6 -

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)
in scholarly communication - working with
communities to develop resources for
multilingualism, gender equity and accessible
and inclusive websites

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Acronyms

ATAG	Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines
C4DISC	Coalition for Diversity and Inclusion in Scholarly Communications
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
COPE	Committee on Publication Ethics
CC	Creative Commons
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional open Access publishing Models to Advance Scholarly communication
DINI	Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment

EDI	Equity, Diversity and Inclusion
EDIB	Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging
EQSIP	Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GEP	Gender Equity Plan
I4OC	Initiative for Open Citations
IP	Institutional Publisher
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
LSE	London School of Economics
ND	No Derivatives
OA	Open Access
OABN	Open Access Books Network
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OPERAS	Open scholarly communication in the European Research Area for Social sciences and humanities
PID	Persistent Identifier
PLS	Plain Language Summary
SA	Share Alike
SIG	Special Interest Group
SP	Service Provider
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Medicine

TRIPLE	Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration
TSV	Tieteellisten seurain valtuuskunta (Federation of Finnish Learned Societies)
UAAG	User Agent Accessibility Guidelines
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines

Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE - CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGÍA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUCILISTE U ZADRU	HR

FFZG	SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	European University Association	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSOE - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAN LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C.I.C.	UK

1. Executive Summary

This report describes the project results, additional literature review, and collaborative process to develop the DIAMAS toolkits and guidelines related to Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB). The focus of this report is on the topics of multilingualism, gender equity, and accessible and inclusive websites as key dimensions of EDIB, which is the seventh core component of the Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024). The report builds on the work summarized in the D3.1 IPSP Best Practices Quality evaluation criteria, best practices, and assessment systems for Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) (Ševkušić & Kuchma, 2023).

The main activity for T4.6 is to develop toolkits and guidelines to help IPSPs to manage and increase the availability of multilingual content, to address language and gender biases in their operations, and to develop more accessible and inclusive websites, content and metadata. Rather than generating original information, the goal was to survey, analyze, curate and repackage existing work in this area. This report explains the collaborative process used to identify such materials and to develop the DIAMAS toolkits and guidelines related to EDIB.

The report opens by contextualizing existing disparities in scholarly publishing. With regard to language, it has been established that using one key language for scholarly publishing presents disadvantages for individuals, research, and society more broadly. Individuals may need to invest more time and money and face higher rejection rates. Privileging one language also privileges one social, cultural and economic perspective and knowledge system, and it hampers uptake of findings by local actors. In terms of gender disparities, men are cited more often, are better represented in key positions, and are overrepresented in research studies. As regards accessible and inclusive websites, content and metadata, inequities arise when designers do not consider aspects such as alt-text, captions, adjustable font/size/colour, or plain or inclusive language. Finally, while it is convenient to study dimensions independently, they may intersect, meaning that a person who is marginalized along one dimension may also be marginalized along others, with cumulative effects.

EDIB issues are sensitive and complex, and it can be intimidating for IPSPs to figure out how to proceed. To develop the toolkits and guidelines, two main approaches were used. First, the existing DIAMAS project documentation was studied, including D2.3 Institutional Publishing in the ERA: results from the DIAMAS survey (Armengou et al., 2023) and D3.3

Report on the gap analysis results (Brun et al., 2023). These DIAMAS project reports were studied to determine the state of the field with regard to barriers, concerns, gaps, and progress to date. In addition, a large-scale literature review was undertaken, which included not only academic literature but also grey literature (e.g., policies, popularized works, professional magazines). Nearly 600 items were collected, organized and stored in a shared Zotero library for analysis.

EDIB is a cross-cutting issue in scholarly publishing. Therefore, while EDIB is one of the seven core components of the DOAS, some aspects may touch the other six components too. For this reason, the results of the analysis are structured around all seven of the core components of the DOAS. Key findings include the following:

1) Funding: Limited and unstable financial resources pose a challenge for meeting accessibility standards and enriching metadata. To reduce costs related to translation and editing, the use of free AI-based translation technologies, as well as collaborative platforms where scholars can exchange linguistic services, are being actively explored. Training (e.g., in unconscious bias, AI literacy) is one area where surveyed IPSPs see potential for collaborating to save costs.

2) Legal ownership, mission and governance: Gender equity can be seen as an aspect of governance, and multiple reports show women occupying low-paying, precarious posts while men are more likely to have senior decision-making roles. Gender equity plans can help, but only 25% of the IPSPs surveyed have implemented such a plan to date, and others mentioned that guidance is needed.

3) Open Science: Some EDIB dimensions are facets of openness, and open reviews come up frequently. Double or triple anonymization (where identities of authors, reviewers, and editors, are unknown to one another) is a way to reduce gender bias during reviews. Fewer than 20% of the IPSPs surveyed have implemented open reviews, but an additional 30% are considering it. It is important to consider how anonymization and openness of reviews might interact, and to understand different degrees of openness. Multilingual abstracts and plain language summaries offer an entry point into creating a more multilingual and accessible scholarly publishing ecosystem.

4) Editorial management, editorial quality and research integrity: Concerns about lack of diversity among authors, reviewers, and editorial boards came up frequently, and different types of diversity statements and monitoring efforts are ways to address this. Training about unconscious bias, or pointing to existing guidelines and resources on this topic, are

also recommended. Policies about reporting on sample populations in research can also help.

5) Technical service efficiency: A lack of human resources and specialized skills block the implementation of some accessibility-related EDIB measures. It is vital to build accessibility into the workflow rather than dealing with it in an ad hoc way. AI-based tools can support some tasks, such as creating multilingual or enriched metadata, but human expertise remains vital.

6) Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact: Discoverability is tied to language. Impact metrics are hotly debated among IPSPs, who may have concerns that displaying impact metrics for publications in languages other than English could create a negative reinforcement loop (e.g. if these metrics are lower than comparable English-language publications, scholars may not publish there). Citation-based metrics also have implications since publications in languages other than English tend to be cited less often, and policies requiring citation diversity statements, combined with AI-based translation technologies, may help.

7) EDIB: The landscape survey and gap analysis reveal that implementing EDIB is far from standard practice and there is much variation across IPSPs. Additional EDIB points raised include the need for clear guidelines about multilingual publication options, about using inclusive language and about preparing appropriate peer feedback (i.e., separating content issues from language issues). Relaxing word limits (e.g., for abstracts) could allow authors to write in a more accessible way.

Several practical implications, lessons learned, and future possibilities emerged:

- EDIB is complex, but interim measures and stepped approaches can get us started.
- Four main types of gaps exist and can hinder EDIB implementation, including social gaps (different practices), moral gaps (different values), interpretive gaps (different understandings), and practical gaps (different capacities/resources for implementation).
- Identify priorities and try to accomplish some of the more easily achievable targets to begin.
- Technology can play a role, but it must be supported by meaningful policies.
- Accessibility legislation differs between countries and regions, so be aware of local requirements.
- Compliance (for accessibility) is not a one-off issue but requires ongoing commitment.

- Take a holistic view because fixing one problem could risk introducing another.
- Remember the project scope, but be open to learning from related areas.

To engage the community, two webinars were held and surveys were developed. In addition, a blog post was published on the LSE impact blog, and all activities were shared widely on social media. The team also participated in a mutual learning exercise with OPERAS and OABN. Feedback on the DIAMAS toolkits and guidelines was then incorporated into revised versions of these resources.

2. Scope

The main activity for T4.6 is to develop toolkits, guidelines, and training materials to help IPSPs to manage and increase the availability of multilingual content and to address language and gender biases in their operations. A first step in this process is to understand more about the existing practices and challenges of IPSPs, as well as to identify existing resources, policies, good practices, potential solutions, known gaps and other related ideas that have been presented in the academic and grey literature.

The publishing standards developed in the project were referred to with the name Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing (EQSIP) for Diamond Open Access ([Rico-Castro et al., 2024](#)) however, the final version the standard (EQSIP V2.0) has been renamed as the Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024), and future mentions of the final version of the standards will also be using that new name within this report.

The DOAS standard addresses seven core components of scholarly publishing:

1. Funding
2. Legal ownership, mission and governance
3. Open Science
4. Editorial management, editorial quality, and research integrity
5. Technical service efficiency
6. Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact
7. Equity, Diversity and Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB): multilingualism, gender equity.

Building on the initial work summarized in D3.1 IPSP Best Practices Quality evaluation criteria, best practices, and assessment systems for Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) ([Ševkušić & Kuchma, 2023](#)), the current report takes a deeper dive into matters related specifically to core component **7. Equity, Diversity and Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB): multilingualism, gender equity**. While EDIB is crucial enough to warrant the status of a core component, it is important to recognize that, as noted in D3.1 IPSP Best Practices Quality evaluation criteria, best practices, and assessment systems for Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) ([Ševkušić & Kuchma, 2023](#)), EDIB matters are cross-cutting and so may emerge within or be relevant to the other core components,

such as in themes concerning stakeholders, governance, IPSP and journal websites and their content/metadata, decision-making around content, and open science practices.

The present report focuses on providing a summary and analysis of existing resources, policies, good practices, potential solutions and known gaps regarding EDIB in the context of scholarly publishing and scholarly communication with the aim of presenting a high-level overview of the current landscape and pointing to material that can be incorporated into the toolsuites and training materials for IPSPs.

3. Background and context

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) is a conceptual framework to support the fair treatment and full participation of all people, especially in the workplace, including populations who have historically been under-represented or subject to discrimination because of their background, identity, disability, etc.

- **Equity:** Removing systemic barriers and biases to enable everyone to have equal opportunities.
- **Diversity:** Ensuring that people of different sexes, genders, abilities, career stages, races, ethnicities, geographic and institutional locations, and linguistic and cultural backgrounds are represented in the community.
- **Inclusion:** Ensuring that all individuals are visible, heard and considered.
- **Belonging:** Treating everyone as a full member of the community and helping them to thrive.

In the context of scholarly communication, several disparities have emerged, including linguistic and gender disparities, as well as inequities with regard to accessibility (e.g. of websites). To dismantle discrimination in scholarly publishing, more institutional publishers and service providers (IPSPs) want to implement measures to address various facets of EDIB. This section provides a brief overview of the problems and emerging responses.

3.1 Disparities in scholarly publishing

3.1.1 Language disparities

With regard to language, it is well known that over the past several decades, English has become established as the key language of scholarly communication ([Gordin, 2015](#)). In principle, there can be some advantages to using a single language for research and dissemination: if everyone adopts a single lingua franca, researchers around the world need only master this one language (instead of several) to communicate with all other researchers ([Gordin, 2015](#)). However, in practice, it has become increasingly clear that adopting a single language for scholarly communication also has numerous disadvantages ([Ramírez-Castañeda, 2020](#)). For instance, non-Anglophone scholars typically invest more time in reading, writing and proofreading in English, spend more money to have their work edited, and receive more rejections and requests for extensive revisions, all of which may contribute to a lower overall productivity, which can in turn impact career prospects

([Amano et al., 2023](#)). Meanwhile, those who do choose to publish in other languages may be cited less often, which can also negatively impact their careers ([Breeze, 2015](#); [Desrochers & Lariviere, 2016](#); [Di Bitetti & Ferreras, 2017](#)).

Beyond the implications for individual researchers, the use of a single language for scholarly publishing has other drawbacks. By forcing the bulk of knowledge creation through an Anglo-Saxon lens, we are moving towards an epistemological monoculture ([Bennett, 2015](#)), which has a number of consequences. Firstly, it limits the nature of what gets investigated, since major international journals are less likely to publish on subjects that have a regional focus, such as local species of flora or fauna ([Amano, Berdejo-Espinola, et al., 2021](#)). Furthermore, granting one language a privileged position sets up a situation where vital research that is published in other languages is likely to be overlooked ([Nuñez & Amano, 2021](#)), thus hampering global progress on important issues, such as planetary biodiversity and conservation ([Amano, Berdejo-Espinola, et al., 2021](#)) or global health ([Xiang et al., 2020](#)). Finally, it limits the uptake of research findings by regional or local actors, such as policy makers or community members, who may not have a high level of competence in English ([Amano et al., 2016](#)).

3.1.2 Gender disparities

Likewise, with regard to gender diversity, the lack of equitable or fair representation of people of different genders in various roles in scholarly publishing can have consequences for individuals as well as for research and society more broadly.

Problems stemming from lack of gender diversity can begin in the earliest stages of research. For instance, if there is inadequate representation of genders in a study sample, the results could be less useful overall, while the absence of gender-related reporting could hinder the translation of research into practice (e.g., for healthcare) ([Sugimoto et al., 2019](#)).

The degree and nature of gender diversity can differ greatly from one discipline to the next, with some being more dominated by men (e.g. engineering) and others by women (e.g. nursing). Nonetheless, across a range of disciplines and regions, it has been observed that women are underrepresented as authors, and particularly in prestigious authorship positions such as first, last or corresponding author ([Sebo & Schwarz, 2023](#)). Moreover, articles authored by women are cited less often ([Chatterjee & Werner, 2021](#)). In part, this perceived lack of productivity and expertise results in fewer women in senior ranks (e.g.,

full professors) and in prestigious positions (e.g., journal editors). One reason put forward for the underrepresentation of women authors is that reviewer pools and editorial boards also contain a majority of men, who may exhibit unconscious bias towards women, leading to a higher manuscript rejection rate ([Fox & Paine, 2019](#)).

Finally, another way that gender disparity can manifest itself in scholarly publishing is when fewer women are awarded leadership or executive roles within IPSPs ([Li & Zhao, 2023](#)).

3.1.3 Accessible and inclusive websites, content and metadata

Improving accessibility and inclusion for people with disabilities is another facet of EDIB that is relevant to scholarly publishing ([Holt et al., 2023](#)). Accessibility refers to designing products or services to ensure that both content and digital functionality are available to everyone, regardless of abilities or impairments. Accessible designs ensure both direct access (i.e., unassisted) and indirect access (i.e., compatible with assistive technology such as screen readers). Meanwhile, inclusion involves proactively creating an environment where people feel welcomed, respected, and valued. When accessibility and inclusion are not taken into consideration by IPSPs, some users may be unable to access their products or services, or may feel uncomfortable doing so. In some cases, the IPSP may even be non-compliant with regulations (e.g. European Directive on the accessibility of the websites and mobile applications of public sector bodies). A first step toward accessibility is awareness of the need to make content and functionality (e.g., on websites or in digital publications) accessible to everyone; however, different regions have different requirements ([Initiative \(WAI\), n.d.](#)).

Inequities arise when website designers do not consider aspects such as presenting text in a logical reading order; ensuring that font, colour, size, and line spacing are adjustable; separating presentation and content; providing image descriptions and alt-text for pictures and captions or transcripts for videos; including page numbers; and using metadata to communicate accessibility modes and features of resources ([Creating Accessible Content, n.d.](#)).

Other potential stumbling blocks for accessibility and inclusion include language choices. For instance, readers with lower literacy or using a non-dominant language may struggle to make sense of highly specialized language ([Rosenberg et al., 2023](#)). Likewise, readers may be alienated by language that is not respectful or sensitive with regard to diversity ([Ashwell](#)

et al., 2023), such as writing that simply adopts the point of view that represents whatever group is considered to be the default group or groups that have traditionally held more power, such as Western Anglo-Saxon institutions, men, White people, or able-bodied people. Looking beyond text, it is important to use inclusive images and data visualization techniques as well.

3.1.4 Other disparities and intersectionality

Although the focus of this report is on EDIB as it pertains to linguistic and gender equity, it is worth noting that other facets of EDIB, such as racial, ethnic and sexual orientation discrimination (Salazar et al., 2021), and lack of representation from certain geographical regions (e.g. Global South) (Espin et al., 2017; Gomez et al., 2022; Palser et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2023), are also present and need to be addressed in the scholarly community. Moreover, it is important to recognize the impact of intersectionality in this context. Intersectionality refers to the cumulative way that the effects of different forms of discrimination (e.g. linguistic, gender, geographical, racial and socioeconomic discrimination) combine, overlap, or intersect, particularly in the case of people who are marginalized (Crenshaw, 1991). For instance, an analysis of authors who published in *The Lancet Global Health* reveals that women authors are underrepresented, but when the data is disaggregated by geographical location, greater disparities emerged, with the highest gender gap existing among authors from low-income countries (Morgan et al., 2019). In another example, Valeria Ramírez-Castañeda points out in an interview how language, race and socioeconomic status can intersect to create cumulative disadvantages for scholars:

“Now that we (in the U.S.) are speaking about the Black community, in many places, including Colombia, race means socioeconomic differences, poverty,” she said. “We don’t see a lot of Black scientists from Colombia, not only because being from a political minority and being a scientist is difficult, but also because of English.” (Sanders, 2022)

3.2 Emerging response to disparities in scholarly publishing

In response to many of the challenges outlined in section 3.1 (Disparities in scholarly publishing), various actors within the scholarly publishing community have begun to take steps to redress some of these issues. For instance, in response to some of the problems arising from the use of a single language for science, some actors in the scholarly publishing community are now advocating to increase multilingualism, such as through the

Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication (Federation Of Finnish Learned Societies et al., 2019). The Coalition for Diversity and Inclusion in Scholarly Communications (C4DISC) was founded in 2017 by ten trade and professional associations that represent organizations and individuals working in scholarly publishing, and their mission is to discuss and address issues of equity, inclusion, diversity, and accessibility in scholarly communication (“Coalition for Diversity and Inclusion in Scholarly Communications,” n.d.). Meanwhile, UNESCO’s “Recommendation on Open Science” (UNESCO, 2021) also calls for actions to reduce disparities related to language, gender, disability, and more.

A main objective of the DIAMAS project is to build on the work of these advocacy groups and to respond to these calls to action in a concrete way, such as by providing toolkits that IPSPs can use to identify, mitigate, reduce and eventually correct or eliminate linguistic, gender and accessibility disparities in scholarly publishing.

4. Methodology

Two main sources were used to compile this report: existing DIAMAS reports (i.e., a survey of current practices of IPSPs ([Armengou et al., 2023](#)) and a gap analysis ([Brun et al., 2023](#))), as well as a broader literature survey to identify issues, gaps, good practices, and potential solutions relating to linguistic, gender and accessibility disparities in scholarly publishing.

4.1 Existing DIAMAS reports

Some preliminary findings were already available from a survey ([Armengou et al., 2023](#)) and a gap analysis ([Brun et al., 2023](#)) that were carried out in earlier phases of the DIAMAS project. In some cases, we consulted the draft versions of the reports as they became available. The specific version that was consulted in each case has been specified.

4.1.1 Survey of IPSPs

A detailed description of the survey and survey process can be found in the report entitled D2.3 Institutional Publishing in the ERA: results from the DIAMAS survey ([Armengou et al., 2023](#)). In brief, as outlined in the introductory section of the survey itself as it was distributed to respondents, the DIAMAS group conducted a survey of IPSPs in order “to map how this sector of scholarly communication is currently organized in order to understand existing challenges and begin to develop resources, tools, policies and strategies which support the relevant stakeholders”. The target group for the survey consisted of IPSPs in European countries, most of which belong to the ERA. Publishers of academic journals are well represented in the survey given that the initial list of target publishers was drawn up based on information gathered from databases of scholarly journals; however, efforts were also made to fill the gaps by contacting other organizations (e.g. book publishers, organizations focusing on other types of service provision for publishing).

The broad scope of the project meant that there was an almost limitless potential for questions, but the survey developers tried to balance the need for data against the time required to complete the survey. In addition to two introductory sections (for demographics), the survey contained seven main sections – one for each of the seven core components of DOAS, including EDIB. The survey was developed in English but then translated and distributed in nine other languages (Croatian, French, German, Italian, Polish, Romanian, Spanish, Turkish and Ukrainian), which were selected based on coverage and on expectations about how many additional/improved responses they would generate.

In order to lighten the load for both translation and analysis, free text answers were kept to a minimum.

Implemented online using Qualtrics, the DIAMAS survey ran for approximately seven weeks between 21 March and 10 May 2023. A total of 704 responses were received, but following data cleaning, some of these had to be discarded (e.g. duplicates, responses from outside the targeted geographic area). In the end, 685 valid responses from 43 countries across the ERA were included in the analysis. However, the responses are not evenly spread across the ERA. For example, Serbia, Croatia, Spain, France and Italy are well represented (together accounting for more than 50% of the total set of responses), whereas a long tail of 22 other countries combined account for less than 10% of the total number of responses. The disparity likely reflects a combination of country size and actual number of IPSPs in each country, as well as effects of dissemination strategies and outreach/uptake. The researchers therefore urge caution with regard to making broad claims about the landscape of institutional publishing in a particular region or country since some may be over- or underrepresented in survey responses. In particular, the researchers indicate that it is likely that Eastern Europe is underrepresented as a region and that very small publishers are underrepresented across all regions.

A complete description of the survey analysis can be found in D2.3 Institutional Publishing in the ERA: results from the DIAMAS survey ([Armengou et al., 2023](#)). In the remainder of this present report (e.g., in [section 5](#) (Analysis and discussion)), the focus will be on analyzing those results from the survey that pertain specifically to EDIB, with a particular emphasis on multilingualism, gender equity and accessibility.

4.1.2 Gap analysis

The main purpose of the gap analysis was to support a transition from EQSIP v1 to DOAS. As such, the gap analysis report contains a detailed analysis of each part of EQSIP v1 with a view to identifying any existing gaps that need to be addressed when developing DOAS. In addition to using the landscape data, the gap analysis authors performed web scraping to uncover more details. In the case of EDIB, there are both data and tables from the landscape, as well as additional information derived from reviewing the websites of participants who responded to the landscape survey, as well as focus groups with some survey participants.

Four main types of gaps were identified as existing between EQSIP v1 and the IPSPs:

- 1) **Social gaps:** some practices, categories or norms outlined in EQSIP v1 are unknown, irrelevant, or ignored by some IPSPs.

- 2) **Moral gaps:** some values outlined in EQSIP v1 are not shared by some IPSPs.
- 3) **Interpretative gaps:** while both EQSIP v1 and IPSPs share a common goal, they don't agree on its interpretation.
- 4) **Practical gaps:** there is an agreement on every other level, but actualization of a standard is problematic (e.g. for financial, technical, staff capacity or other reasons).

A complete description of the gap analysis can be found in [D3.3 Gap Analysis: When EQSIP 1.0 Meets IP Practices](#). In the remainder of this report, only elements from the gap analysis that are pertinent to the EDIB issues of multilingualism, gender equity and accessibility will be discussed.

4.2 Literature

The literature search was carried out by using keywords from the fields of scholarly publishing and EDIB to query academic databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, ERIC, MLA and Google Scholar. In an effort to capture grey literature, searches were also conducted in the Dimensions database, as well as on the world wide web more generally. The list of references for retrieved articles were also consulted to identify additional relevant material (i.e., snowball search).

The searches were conducted in English, French and Spanish, although some material in other languages (e.g., German) was identified using the snowball search technique. We did not place any restrictions on disciplines but were instead open to content from all domains.

Given that EDIB is a dynamic system where societal norms have shifted over time, prompting changes in policies and practices, we focused primarily on recent literature that was published in the past ten years (since 2014). However, some older literature may be cited if it contains a relevant point not raised elsewhere.

The goal of search was not to be exhaustive, but to capture a range of opinions, experiences, practices and suggestions that could be considered when developing toolkits, guidelines and training materials. In the end, nearly 600 items were collected and consulted, though not all of the items have been specifically cited in this report. Readers who wish to consult the broader collection of materials gathered for this project can find them in the [DIAMAS WP4 Zotero library](#).

The literature was analyzed to identify information about EDIB – particularly with regard to multilingualism, gender equity and web accessibility and inclusion – in relation to scholarly publishing. Similar and related topics were grouped together and summarized, and the information in [section 5](#) (Analysis) has been organized according to the seven core components of ESQIP.

The analysis presented some challenges. The works gathered for the literature review are heterogeneous, and the degree of pertinence of EDIB to each of the seven core components differs. Some documents raise problems but do not offer solutions, while others make suggestions for improvements, but these suggestions may not have been tested or verified. Some documents were formulated with commercial publishing rather than Open Access (OA) in mind and so some of their recommendations may not align with OA practices. The majority of documents address journal publications rather than other types of research outputs. Therefore, the findings of this literature survey will need to be adapted and expanded to better fit the profile of the IPSPs who are stakeholders in the DIAMAS project. Although this literature survey cannot provide all the information necessary to create a robust set of toolkits, guidelines and training materials, it can provide a foundation on which to build, especially when considered alongside the findings of the IPSP survey described in [section 4.1](#) (Survey of IPSPs).

5. Analysis and discussion

This section combines an analysis of EDIB-related points that emerged from the survey and gap analysis of the IPSPs, along with an analysis of EDIB-related points that emerged from the literature survey. It begins with some general observations, but the bulk of the analysis is structured according to the seven core components of DOAS. Recall that as noted in [section 2](#) (Scope), while EDIB is itself one of the core components, issues relating to EDIB are cross-cutting and may emerge within or be relevant to the other core components. Therefore, this analysis also considers EDIB issues as they are related to the other six core components of DOAS. Within each section, the analysis is divided into a discussion of the survey results and a discussion of the literature.

5.1 General observations

Questions 1-10 on the survey provided information on the basic characteristics of the

IPSPs that participated in the survey.

5.1.1 Survey and gap analysis

As is typical in surveys, the opening questions seek to gather some information about the overall profile of the IPSPs that responded to the survey, including their country and region (Q2), and whether they identified primarily as an institutional publisher (IP) or service provider (SP) (Q8). In addition to being characteristics in their own right, these three attributes (country, region and type of IPSP) also serve as background variables for further analysis of other characteristics. In addition, a number of the introductory questions may be directly or indirectly relevant to EDIB.

As revealed in Q2, the regions of Southern Europe and Western Europe are well represented, with 47% and 22% of the responses respectively. The number of responses obtained for Northern Europe (16%) and Eastern Europe (12%) is lower, while the number of responses received from other ERA regions outside the EU (e.g. Northern Africa, Southwest Asia) was too small to permit detailed analysis.

Language plays an important role in many aspects of publishing, including the languages used in publications, language diversity, ability for authors to publish in the language of their choice, translation issues, languages supported by submission systems, and languages used on service provider websites. However, Q3 focused specifically on publication languages. A total of 37 different languages are mentioned in the responses, including all official EU languages except Maltese. English is mentioned most often, with over 95% of IPSPs selecting it; however, only about 40% of responses mentioned it as the primary publication language. Of the 379 responses that do not list English as the primary language, 87% list it as the second language, and an additional 10% as the third, fourth or fifth language. Among the responses, French, Spanish, German, Italian, Serbian and Croatian are mentioned as one of the five most frequently used languages; however, it is important to recall that many of these languages correspond to one of the countries that had a high response rate to the survey. What does seem clear is that many IPSPs accept English-language manuscripts in addition to manuscripts in the main language(s) of their country.

Question 4 asks IPSPs about their membership in a variety of organizations, associations or coalitions, including the Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication (Federation of Finnish Learned Societies et al., 2019). Approximately 5% of the IPSPs surveyed are signatories of the Helsinki Initiative, which could suggest that there

is a relatively low awareness of this initiative given that Question 3 indicated that many IPSPs do operate in more than one language.

Question 7 focuses on staff size, which may affect an IPSPs ability to take action on one or more EDIB dimensions. The responses show that a very large majority of IPSPs are small or very small, with more than 75% having five or fewer paid staff members.

Finally, Question 10 addressed discipline, which may affect some EDIB dimensions. For instance, some disciplines are known to be unbalanced in terms of gender (e.g. engineering tends to have a higher proportion of men, while nursing or translation have higher proportions of women). In addition, different disciplinary cultures can influence choices such as publication languages. The survey results show that most of the IPSPs that responded work in the Social Sciences (55%) and Humanities (54%), while the more STEM-oriented disciplines are mentioned less often, although still in substantial numbers, including Natural Sciences (26.9%), Engineering and Technology (23%), and Medical and Health Sciences (21%). Additionally, 45% of IPSPs indicate that they are Multidisciplinary.

With regard to the gap analysis, manual coding of the websites of survey participants helped to shed light on any differences between the participants' perceptions and their actual practices. Of the 32 EDIB-related items that were included in EQSIP v1, 24 (75%) were included in the web coding. The website analysis reveals that in some cases, there are significant gaps between the IPSPs' declaration that they have addressed an EDIB dimension and the public display of doing so.

An additional approach used in the gap analysis was online focus groups with 3 to 5 participants. These focus groups were conducted in countries with the highest number of respondents to the survey: Spain (2 focus groups), France (1), Great Britain (1), Croatia (1), and Serbia (1). Two additional focus groups were conducted: one for Scandinavian publishers with a single journal and one for service providers. The focus groups do not permit wide generalizations, but they can help to uncover some of the reasons why IPSPs do or do not address certain EDIB dimensions.

5.1.3 Literature

The literature reveals that EDIB concerns in scholarly publishing are being discussed in a wide range of regions. For instance, [\(Liani et al., 2021\)](#) report that cultural norms in sub-Saharan Africa place a higher expectation on women for taking on domestic labour,

leaving them less time to devote to scholarly activities such as publishing, which in turn impacts career progression. Meanwhile ([Ramírez-Castañeda, 2020](#)) notes that the expectation to publish in English poses a barrier to researchers in Colombia, while ([Mu, 2020](#)) makes a similar observation with regard to scholars in China. For their part, ([Bajerski & Przygoński, 2018](#)) report that East-Central European researchers also face language bias, such as infrequent citations of their work as compared to Anglophone and Western European researchers.

Issues related to the additional labour and specialized knowledge needed for multilingual publishing are raised by ([Perera, 2016](#)), who notes that the workflow can be optimized for least complexity or the shortest production time, but usually not both.

Different dimensions of EDIB and their relation to scholarly publishing are also being actively discussed in a wide variety of disciplines, such as environmental science ([Amano et al., 2023](#)), ophthalmology ([Sverdlichenko et al., 2022](#)), geography ([Bajerski & Przygoński, 2018](#)), chemistry ([Deng & Flynn, 2023](#)), mathematics ([Topaz & Sen, 2016](#)), addiction studies ([Bahji et al., 2023](#)) and social sciences and humanities ([Kulczycki et al., 2020](#)).

5.2 Funding

Funding: description of the funding model, OA business model, transparency in listing all funding sources, etc.

5.2.1 Survey and gap analysis

A combined total of 68% of IPSPs reported that a lack of financial resources poses an important or very important challenge when seeking to meet accessibility standards. Supplying and enriching metadata (potentially in multiple languages), was identified as another resource-related challenge by 23% of IPSPs.

In terms of areas where IPSPs see potential for collaborating with other organizations to try to save costs, the category of training, support and or advice on publishing policies and best practices was the category identified by the highest number of IPSPs at 45%. This could potentially include training on reducing unconscious bias or on machine translation literacy or improving translatability, for example, as well as other EDIB-related issues. When asked to specify additional suggestions for saving costs through collaboration in the “Other” category, some IPSPs specifically mentioned interlingual translation. Interlingual

translation also comes up as a specific example when IPSPs had the opportunity to share particular types of costs that pose challenges.

The survey revealed that IPSPs draw on a diverse range of funding to support their activities. While stable sources are highly desirable, 41% of IPSPs noted that “fixed and permanent subsidies from parent organizations” are not available to them, and so periodic and time limited grants are also common. However, some EDIB activities – such as translation or accessibility – are not one-off activities, meaning it can be challenging to sustain them without stable funding. Likewise, the source of a grant may determine what it can be spent on. For example, a government might be willing to fund a local language but not a foreign one, or vice versa.

As noted in D2.3 Institutional Publishing in the ERA: results from the DIAMAS survey ([Armengou et al., 2023](#)), the organizational efforts needed to secure funding from different streams and sources or to fulfill the funding criteria must clearly place a considerable burden on many IPSPs. This may be a partial explanation for why a high number of EDIB dimensions have not yet been addressed by many IPSPs (see [section 5.8](#) EDIB).

The survey did not ask any questions that directly link the issue of funding to gender equity, although the issue of precarious employment was raised frequently.

5.2.1 Literature

In Europe, groups such as OPERAS, with its SIG on Multilingualism, are actively exploring cost-effective ways to support translation in scholarly publishing ([Fiorini, 2022](#); [Fiorini et al., 2020](#)). Similar explorations are taking place in other regions also, such as Canada ([Tremblay-Faulkner & Parent, 2023](#)). Such initiatives often involve investigating the possibility of integrating translation technologies into the scholarly publishing process in responsible ways to minimize costs, while keeping humans in the loop to maximize quality ([Bahji et al., 2023](#)).

Rather than turning to translation technology, ([Khelifa et al., 2022](#)) propose implementing a different type of low-cost solution: a volunteer-based peer language proofing and peer translation system into preprint repositories. While highlighting the benefits of such an approach for improving EDIB in research, the authors nonetheless recognize a number of potential challenges, such as: 1) depending on the generosity and goodwill of researchers to provide such services; and 2) quality control of the service provided or received (which could potentially be helped by simultaneously implementing a peer quality check system or a recognition system that keeps track of the performance of contributors).

The literature also points to diverse forms of training or guidelines emerging on topics such as machine translation literacy ([Bowker, 2021](#)), preparing plain language summaries ([Rosenberg et al., 2023](#)), peer review by and for non-native English speakers ([Gradoville et al., 2022](#)), as well as unconscious bias training ([Das Gupta, 2023](#)). Even if IPSPs cannot afford to mount their own training courses, they can point editors, reviewers and authors to existing guidelines. The planned DIAMAS toolsuites should be helpful in this regard.

5.3 Legal ownership, mission and governance

Ownership and governance: legal ownership, mission, and governance.

5.3.1 Survey and gap analysis

Overall, the results of the survey suggest that IPSPs are rather insular in terms of governance and oversight, as well as being inward looking and local in terms of their scholarly representation. Roughly half of the IPSPs who responded to the survey appear to need help in professionalizing their governance practices and financial audits, and in reaching out to the broader scholarly community to ensure scholarly legitimacy beyond their local context. An examination of regional or national answers to the survey questions does not show any clear trend: all countries and regions have substantial subsets of IPSPs that lack professional oversight of governance, finances, and outside scholarly representation.

Gender equity and linguistic diversity can be seen as governance issues, but no questions in the governance section of the survey focused directly on these aspects. However, [section 5.8](#) (Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging: multilingualism, gender equity) does delve into some of these issues, such as having a Gender Equity Plan (GEP) – a measure that has been implemented by 25% of IPSPs.

5.3.1 Literature

Achieving an equitable level of gender representation can be viewed as an aspect of governance. However, ([Li & Zhao, 2023](#)) report on challenges faced by women in the publishing industry in China that were revealed as part of their survey of 3372 Chinese publishing practitioners. While women occupy nearly 70% of the positions and tend to be more highly educated, men tend to enjoy higher salaries and better career prospects. Among the survey respondents, only 10.53% of women occupied a senior management role

as compared to 19.82% of men. Meanwhile, [\(Toth, 2021\)](#) explores the situation in the Canadian publishing industry and finds that here, too, women are underrepresented in executive positions and receive less favourable wages.

Given that men occupy more senior positions in the publishing industry, more of the key decision-making in IPSPs is likely to be carried out by men, which may call into question the fairness, transparency and inclusiveness of the policies, policy development processes, and policy outcomes within the publishing industry. Gender equity plans are one way to address this problem.

Nevertheless, while the gender dimension is one of the main EDIB focuses of the DIAMAS project, some other dimensions were included in the DIAMAS survey (e.g. sexuality, ethnicity, disability, language). It is therefore worth noting that [\(Toth, 2021\)](#) emphasizes that inequity in the publishing industry goes beyond a lack of gender parity and extends to other historically marginalized communities. Moreover, it is often intersectional. In the words of [\(Toth, 2021, p. iii\)](#), there are numerous ways in which “women who aren’t able-bodied, straight, white, and cis-gendered face unique obstacles in the [publishing] industry.” Therefore, equity-related governance policies in the publishing industry will need to look beyond gender.

5.4 Open science

Open science practices: OA policy, copyright and licensing, open peer review, data sharing, new approaches to research assessment, etc.

5.4.1 Survey and gap analysis

Overall, the survey responses revealed a high commitment to open scholarship practices on the part of IPSPs; however, the DIAMAS survey team cautioned that several issues with the sampling and the wording of some questions may have skewed the results in this direction. The survey also reveals considerable regional variety, as well as differences linked to the discipline as well as to the size and nature (for profit vs non-profit) of the IPSP.

Questions about the adoption of open science principles are particularly pertinent to the question of EDIB. The survey sought to uncover the willingness of IPSPs to adopt positive practices associated with openness and transparency in scholarly communication. Since transparency and inclusion are often cited as key tenets of openness, answers to the

survey questions about open citations (Q27) and open peer review (Q28) could have implications for some dimensions of EDIB.

With regard to the question of making references openly available according to the principles of the Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC), nearly half of the respondents answered either “I don’t know”, “No”, or “Not applicable”, which suggests a possible lack of awareness about the standards or possible lack of technical capabilities, and a further consultation with the communities is needed to probe more deeply.

With regard to open peer review, just 17% of IPSPs have already enabled some form of open peer review, with a small number currently experimenting. However, close to half (45%) of IPSPs responded “No”, although an additional 29% said that they may consider implementing open peer review at a later stage.

5.4.2 Literature

In early 2023, the Ecological Society of America held a workshop that focused specifically on the intersection of EDIB and Open Access in scholarly publishing ([Landis et al., 2023](#)). The workshop explored barriers and solutions, and concluded that EDIB and OA share many values and are very compatible overall. As summarized by ([Landis et al., 2023, pp. 76-77](#)), the following takeaway messages emerged from the 2-day workshop, which concluded that journals would benefit from:

- Establishing systems to collect baseline data to better document the demographic make-up of peer reviewers, editorial board, and authors.
- Training editors, editorial board members, journal staff, and other volunteer groups to recognize and intercept biases in peer review, selecting papers for publication, and/or the application of editorial processes.
- Creating and adopting actionable diversity building plans.
- Taking action steps to avoid editorial boards’ lack of representation of women and racial and ethnic groups.
- Establishing action steps to include participation among small academic and research institutions.
- Remaining committed to avoiding gender, racial/ethnic, and geographic disparities in scholarly publishing.
- Maintaining an intentional focus on using policies and procedures to advance diversity, equity, and inclusion in OA publishing.
- Taking steps to make research accessible to low- and middle-income countries.

- Taking steps to provide better opportunities for researchers from and in low- and middle-income countries to be able to publish their work without a high-cost burden.
- Adopting, implementing, and utilizing findings from author surveys to identify diversity strengths, weaknesses, and barriers to participation among authors, editorial board members, and journal staff.
- Ensuring open access to scholarly information can be achieved through cross-sector partnerships between government, international organizations, higher education, philanthropic organizations, learned societies, and libraries.

The literature reveals that language can be viewed as a facet of openness. For instance, in the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science ([UNESCO, 2021, p. 17](#)), this organization emphasizes that open science should “embrace a diversity of ... languages”, and that it should also support the needs of “the wider public and knowledge holders beyond the traditional scientific community.” The first can be achieved by supporting different forms of multilingualism in scholarly publishing ([Sivertsen, 2018](#)), while one way to support the second is through plain language ([Rosenberg et al., 2023](#)).

With regard to multilingualism, this can take different forms, such as allowing the submission of titles, abstracts, keywords and supplemental information in different languages ([Nolde-Lopez et al., 2023](#)), or choosing a Creative Commons (CC) license that permits translation (e.g. Share Alike (SA) rather than No Derivatives (ND)) ([Steigerwald et al., 2022](#)).

With regard to plain language, this could include encouraging or requiring authors to submit a plain language summary (PLS) and adopting a standard, such as the Open Pharma recommendations for PLS, which outline minimum standards, providing concise guidance on PLS for authors, editors, and other stakeholders involved in PLS development ([Rosenberg, 2022](#)).

EDIB also has implications for other open science practices, such as open citations. For example, bias may emerge in citation practices, meaning that groups such as women ([Chatterjee & Werner, 2021](#)), scholars from the Global South ([Gomez et al., 2022](#)), or authors writing in languages other than English ([Breeze, 2015](#); [Desrochers & Lariviere, 2016](#)) may be cited less often. Open citation practices, along with strategies such as requiring citation diversity statements ([Ray et al., 2024](#); [Zurn et al., 2020](#)), could help to expose such biases

or provide a means of monitoring and reducing them. Therefore, raising awareness about open citation and citation diversity will be a key step forward.

The literature also raises the importance of considering how a fully open review may impact groups that have historically been victims of bias in scholarly publishing (e.g. women, non-Anglophones, scholars from the Global South), or groups that may continue to privilege those who have historically benefitted (e.g. by having an affiliation with a prestigious institution). As noted by [\(Budden et al., 2008\)](#), double-anonymous peer review (i.e., where the identities of the authors and reviewers are not known to one another) has been shown to reduce gender bias. A more recent systematic review on this topic by [\(Kern-Goldberger et al., 2022, p. 43\)](#) reveals mixed results (i.e., some journals showed improved gender equity when double-anonymization was used, while others did not); however, the authors conclude “there is reasonable evidence that gender bias may exist in scientific publishing and that double-blinding can mitigate its impact.” Meanwhile, [\(Brodie et al., 2021, p. 957\)](#) have suggested that triple-anonymous review (i.e., where the identities of authors, reviewers and editors are not known to one another) can help to further “reduce the biases that negatively affect under-represented and minority scientists, ultimately better supporting equity in scientific publishing.” However, according to the results of an investigation by [\(Conklin & Singh, 2022\)](#), implementing a triple-anonymized review process incurs numerous additional inconveniences and does not lead to the same improvements noted when switching from single- to double-anonymized review. There are many different views on the issue of anonymized vs open reviews, but one important point for IPSPs who are considering implementing open reviews is to be aware that there can be different degrees of openness (e.g. open identities vs open reports). Crucially, IPSPs should reflect carefully on the options and seek to strike the right balance between making peer review as transparent as possible, but as closed as necessary (e.g., to reduce bias or protect sensitive information)[\(Shoham & Pitman, 2021\)](#).

5.5 Editorial management, editorial quality, and research integrity

Editorial management, editorial quality, and research integrity.

5.5.1 Survey and gap analysis

The make-up of an editorial board and reviewer pool are directly related to questions of EDIB, as are some types of policies (e.g. recruitment of editors, reporting on sample populations) and guidelines (e.g. how to reduce unconscious bias).

The survey reveals that nearly 70% of IPSPs are involved in editorial management, including through roles such as recruiting and managing editorial board members (79%), coordinating the peer review process (78%), monitoring the peer review process (78%), sourcing reviewers (75%), or performing basic checks on adherence with the authors' and reviewers' guidelines (73%). With regard to managing editorial quality, 74% of IPSPs are involved in creating quality criteria/enabling compliance, while 91% provide guidelines and instructions.

The most commonly implemented type of peer review is double-anonymized review (76%), followed by single-anonymized review (37%), and editorial screening (33%). The option of triple-anonymized review was not included in the survey. There are some disciplinary differences, notably with regard to single-anonymized vs double-anonymized reviews. Although double-anonymized peer review is the most implemented form of peer review overall, single-anonymized review is more common in Science and Engineering and less common in the Humanities and Social Sciences.

Various types of open reviews were presented to the IPSPs. Open identities are implemented by 13% of IPSPs, open review reports by 7%, and open participation by just 3%.

Policies on research integrity may address questions such as appropriate reporting on the characteristics of population samples used in studies (e.g. reporting the gender of research subjects). Nearly two-thirds of the IPSPs report having a specific policy on research integrity/publication ethics, while 27% report having no policy, and 9% do not know if they have a policy. Responses to this question vary considerably from one region to the next.

5.5.2 Literature

Many discussions about bias related to editorial and peer review processes and participants are present in the literature. The potential for gender bias can emerge in the attribution of authorship ([Sebo & Schwarz, 2023](#)), composition of editorial boards ([Gallivan et al., 2021](#); [Topaz & Sen, 2016](#)), invitations to write editorials ([Thomas et al., 2019](#)), peer reviewer pools ([Smith et al., 2023](#)) and citation practices ([Chatterjee & Werner, 2021](#)). Likewise, bias relating to language or country of origin can also emerge in the composition of editorial boards ([Espin et al., 2017](#)) or peer reviewer pools ([Smith et al., 2023](#)), and citation practices ([Di Bitetti & Ferreras, 2017](#)). Additionally, a number of authors emphasize that bias can be intersectional ([Palser et al., 2022](#)).

With regard to potential solutions, suggestions include creating meaningful diversity statements and monitoring practices to diversify editorial boards ([Nuñez et al., 2019](#); [Parker, 2019](#)) or reviewer pools ([Smith et al., 2023](#)), asking authors to include a citation diversity statement ([Zurn et al., 2020](#)) limiting author given names to first and middle initials rather than complete names to better mask the author's gender ([Fox & Paine, 2019](#)), and providing guidelines or training about unconscious bias ([Gradoville et al., 2022](#)). Strategies that involve implementing double-anonymized ([Budden et al., 2008](#)) or triple-anonymized ([Brodie et al., 2021](#)) reviews are also suggested, although as discussed previously, concerns have been raised about the effectiveness of these solutions as compared to the efforts required to implement them ([Conklin & Singh, 2022](#)).

While there is evidence to suggest that gender and language bias are present in different regions and disciplines, there may nonetheless be some differences in degree. For instance, it is interesting to note that the DIAMAS survey results show that the use of single-anonymized reviewing is much more prevalent in Science and Engineering – disciplines where women are known to be underrepresented. Meanwhile, ([Kern-Goldberger et al., 2022](#)) found evidence that single-anonymized reviewing is likely to lead to worse outcomes for women. Disciplinary differences also emerge in the literature with regard to whether authors are more or less likely to favour publishing in English vs multilingual publishing ([Krawczyk, 2023](#)), and there is a potential risk that they may bring such biases to their activities as peer reviewers or board members also. While there is clearly a need to raise awareness about gender and linguistic bias in the scholarly publishing industry on the whole, some disciplines and regions are more affected than others, pointing to a need for both generalized and targeted policy development and action.

Questions of research integrity also come up in the literature. For instance, if there is inadequate representation of genders in a study sample, the results could be less useful overall, while the absence of gender-related reporting could hinder the translation of research into practice (e.g., for healthcare). Institutional publishing and service providers (IPSPs) can help by implementing policies that require gender-related reporting in journal publications ([Sugimoto et al., 2019](#)). Meanwhile, ([Neimann Rasmussen & Montgomery, 2018](#)) discuss the implications of conducting systematic reviews or meta-analyses in English only without being explicit about whether additional languages have been specifically excluded (with appropriate justification). They note that this practice could risk ignoring key data and introducing bias into the review.

5.6 Technical service efficiency

Technical service efficiency: technical strength, interoperability - metadata, ISSN, PIDs, machine readability, and journal website.

5.6.1 Survey and gap analysis

This section of the survey focused on the implementation of technical standards by the IPSPs to gain an understanding of their overall technical capacity. None of the survey questions explicitly linked EDIB dimensions to technical service efficiency. However, as the results show, many of the IPSPs face a series of challenges related to the lack of financial resources (59%), human resources (55%), and expertise (18%) required for their infrastructure and services, which may in turn limit their capacity to implement some types of EDIB measures.

For instance, accessibility-related metadata or multilingual metadata may be considered to be forms of enriched metadata. However, as noted in D2.3 Institutional Publishing in the ERA: results from the DIAMAS survey ([Armengou et al., 2023](#)), notwithstanding the benefits, creating processable files with enriched metadata requires specific skills and consumes effort. A lack of human resources (43%) and a lack of expertise (27%) were identified by IPSPs as the two most important factors hindering their efforts to supply and enrich metadata.

5.6.2 Literature

As emphasized in the literature, accessibility is complex, including from a technical perspective ([Conrad & Kasdorf, 2018](#)). It requires specialized knowledge, and it is not always considered up front but may be treated as an afterthought. In the words of ([Kasdorf, 2018, p. 17](#)), “the extra effort to make a publication accessible is not likely to disappear anytime soon, but current procedures and workflows make it much harder and more costly than it needs to be.” Ensuring that accessibility is properly integrated into the workflow as a strategic and operational priority can help IPSPs to move from having products that are merely “born digital” (i.e., to which accessibility elements and enriched metadata can be added) to ones that are “born accessible” – which is better and cheaper ([Kasdorf, 2018; Turner, 2018](#)).

Another way that metadata could be enriched is by making it multilingual. There is a discussion on multilingual metadata in the report on data enrichment that was produced

as part of the TRIPLE project to develop the GoTriple multilingual search engine ([De Santis, 2022](#)). In this project, machine translation was successfully used to fill in the gaps when multilingual information was missing.

Clearly efforts are already being made to use Natural Language Processing techniques to support the task of enriching metadata ([Brisebois, 2017](#)), and there is evidence in the grey/industry literature to show that companies are actively exploring the potential of technologies and techniques such as AI and machine learning to help further ([Badan, 2021](#); [Campbell, 2023](#)).

5.7 Visibility, communication, marketing and impact

Visibility, including communication, marketing and impact.

5.7.1 Survey and gap analysis

Enhancing visibility and discoverability of publications and their content has direct ties to the question of language. More than half (54%) of the IPSPs would like to see better indexing of their content, although responses vary according to factors such as the IPSP's number of paid employees, budget size, and country. Although fewer than 25% of IPSPs overall identified language as a barrier for indexing-related issues, this varied considerably by region. The DIAMAS survey team hypothesizes that the predominant use of less widely spoken languages might present significant barriers to achieving greater visibility through international indexes. Indeed, examining the data at a regional level reveals that reports of language-related challenges are most pronounced among IPSPs in countries where Bulgarian, Czech, Croatian, Hungarian and Slovak are spoken.

In the survey, the issue of displaying various usage and impact metrics is highly contested from multiple viewpoints. There is a relatively even split between IPSPs that display metrics (42.5%) and those that do not (45.5%), with an additional 12% stating that they do not know. The most frequently used metrics are those that are widely recognized, easily understandable, require minimal technical support, and do not involve fees. These include article-level usage metrics (66%), submission, acceptance, and publication dates (64%), and publication-level usage metrics (43%). For a significant share of respondents, though not a majority, impact metrics hold importance, with 37.9% displaying publication-level impact indicators and 36.4% showing some form of article-level impact indicators. Although there is no specific discussion of the relationship between language and metrics

in the survey or survey analysis, it is possible that some IPSPs may be concerned about creating a potential “negative reinforcement loop” by displaying metrics for publications in languages other than English. For instance, if these metrics appear to be lower than comparable English-language publications, then there is a risk that institutions will not endorse them and scholars will not seek to publish there. Multilingual content has the possibility to reach a broader audience through discoverability services for users searching in different languages, which is a benefit that should not be underestimated also from a metrics perspective.

Another type of metric used by just 12% of visitors is a widget showing the geographical spread of visitors. This type of metric could be useful for identifying not only the regions, but also the associated languages, of visitors and it could thus be informative for helping to decide whether to add a particular language to the service offering of an IPSP.

The survey asks whether IPSPs have a newsletter or social media profiles to inform the community about updates; however, this question does not explore whether language poses any challenge in this regard.

5.7.2 Literature

As mentioned previously, using machine translation tools to translate metadata ([De Santis, 2022](#)) could help to increase visibility or discoverability of scholarly works, although this will not necessarily provide a complete solution. For instance, ([Rovira et al., 2021](#)) investigated Google Scholar’s relevance ranking system and the results of their study point to a bias in multilingual searches conducted in Google Scholar with documents published in languages other than in English being systematically relegated to positions that make them virtually invisible.

Citation-based metrics also have implications for languages given that publications in languages other than English tend to be cited less often than English-language publications ([Di Bitetti & Ferreras, 2017](#)). As noted above, it could be perceived as a risk to display metrics for non-English publications because these may not compare favourably to the metrics for publications in English.

The literature suggests that translating a variety of supporting materials used in the scholarly publishing community could help to promote multilingualism and EDIB, including translating (portions of) an IPSP’s website, diversity statements, submission instructions

for authors, guidelines for peer reviewers, and calls for submissions ([Steigerwald et al., 2022](#)).

5.8 Equity, Diversity Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB): multilingualism, gender equity

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB): multilingualism, gender equity, accessible/inclusive website, content, metadata

5.8.1 Survey and gap analysis

As revealed by the survey of IPSPs, addressing EDIB is far from a standard practice among this group. However, among respondents who claim to have implemented some aspects of EDIB already, language-related elements are the most commonly addressed (30%), followed by gender issues (29%). Although multilingualism and gender are the two elements of primary focus in this report, it was noted previously ([section 3.1.4 Other disparities and intersectionality](#)) that intersectionality is a concern in EDIB. Therefore it is worth observing that other EDIB issues are receiving comparatively little attention, with the following dimensions having been implemented by around one quarter or less of the respondents: age (26%), educational and professional background (25%), ethnicity (22%); socio-economic background (21%), sexual identity (20%), religious background (19%); disability (17%), and caring responsibilities (16%).

A concerning observation is that more than half of the IPSPs (54%) do not appear to have implemented any EDIB dimensions at all. More encouraging is the news that 27% of the IPSPs are addressing three or more dimensions, while 9% are implementing all 10.

However, the gap analysis does reveal some discrepancies between what the IPSPs say they are doing and whether there is public evidence of their actions. For instance, while 29% of IPSPs declare that they have an established code of conduct or non-discrimination or positive discrimination policy, only 17% of the IPSP websites include a public statement on gender equity. Likewise, approximately 20% of IPSP survey responses indicated that they implement and recommend the use of inclusive language, but only 4% display this policy on their website. With regard to an accessibility policy, 32% of IPSPs declare that they have one, but only 21% make it available on their website. With regard to those IPSPs that have not yet implemented many of the ten EDIB dimensions covered in the survey, the dimensions of language, gender and accessibility are the ones that are most commonly

under active development or in a planning stage. Only a small number of IPSPs (15% or fewer) are not planning to implement any measures related to these three dimensions. On the other hand, the relatively high number of IPSPs that are not planning to implement many of the other dimensions (i.e., beyond language, gender and accessibility) could point to a lack of awareness about intersectionality. For instance, only 7% of IPSPs are planning to address caring responsibilities – a dimension that the literature reveals to have a stronger negative affect on women ([Collins, 2020](#); [Malisch et al., 2020](#)).

An interesting observation is the fact that a very common response for almost all of the ten EDIB dimensions surveyed was “not applicable”, which raises questions about the criteria used to make this decision. Do IPSPs interpret applicability as something that they are legally required to do, or do they simply not consider it to be of interest or importance to their stakeholders? Likewise, another relatively common response was “not planning”, and it would be interesting to probe more deeply about the reasons why (e.g. is it a case of prioritization, or of not knowing how to begin tackling the problem?). These or similar questions could be worth posing in future community engagement activities (see [section 7](#) Potential questions for community consultations).

Looking beyond the ten EDIB dimensions, there were 18 specific measures of EDIB included in the survey questionnaire (covering accessibility, gender, multilingualism and EDIB more generally). Overall, the vast majority of IPSPs have implemented at least some of the 18 different kinds of EDIB measures, while only 11% implemented none. The majority of IPSPs (58%) implemented between one and five measures, while 6% implemented ten or more, including just one IPSP that implemented all 18 measures.

There were noticeable differences between the type and number of EDIB dimensions addressed by IPSPs in different regions, which could point to cultural differences, differing legal systems, as well as economic differences.

Multilingualism

Collectively, the IPSPs that responded to the survey offer services in a total of 54 different languages, with the most common being English (83%), French (21%), Spanish (18%), German (17%), and Croatian (15%). The very large gap between the most common language (i.e., English) and the cluster of languages coming in second, third, fourth and fifth place confirms that English continues to be used as a sort of lingua franca and occupies a central position in scholarly publishing. At the other end of the spectrum, there are 18 different languages offered in which services are offered by 5 or fewer IPSPs, including 7 languages offered by just a single IPSP (e.g. Asturian, Georgian, Romani, Scots).

Almost 20% of IPSPs are monolingual, while nearly three quarters of the IPSPs offer services in two or more languages, and 7% did not respond to the language question on the survey. In terms of multilingual service offerings by IPSPs, 42% provide services in two languages, 15% in three languages, 8% in four languages, and 4% in five languages. This is followed by a long tail of IPSPs offering services in a greater number of languages, with one stating that they offer services in 44 different languages.

A clear majority of IPSPs (71%) have already implemented multilingual publishing of abstracts, while a considerable share also support publishing of full texts in multiple languages. The most frequently implemented form is bilingual publishing of different language versions in the same document (33%), followed by simultaneous publishing of different language versions as separate documents (26%), and finally the sequential publishing of different language versions in different journals (13%). Fewer than 10% of IPSPs claim to be in the process of considering or implementing multilingual publishing of full texts, while approximately one-third do not have any such plans.

Almost three quarters of IPSPs support multilingual publishing in at least one of the four forms considered in the survey questionnaire (i.e., multilingual abstracts; bilingual full-text in same document; bilingual full-text simultaneously in separate documents; bilingual full-text sequentially in separate documents). Of these, one quarter support multilingual publishing in just one form, 12% in two of the forms, and 8% in three forms.

With regard to additional types of measures taken to promote language diversity and reduce language bias, the most commonly adopted measure is to provide the abstract in English when the original language is not English (51%). Likewise, translating metadata into English where the original language is other than English (31%), and providing translation or language-checking services to authors (28%) are also relatively common. Less common are approaches such as using toolkits/training to address language bias in peer review or improving machine translation literacy or translation friendly writing (7%). Moreover, just 14% of IPSPs are planning or actively working to implement measures for improving machine translation literacy, while more than one third have no plans to implement either machine translation or toolkits/training to address language bias.

Overall, 58% of IPSPs have implemented at least one of the five proposed measures included in the survey questionnaire for promoting language diversity and reducing language bias: 19% have implemented at least one measure, 21% have implemented two measures, 14% have implemented three measures, 3% have implemented four, and 2% have implemented all five.

With regard to publishing a manuscript in another language in another journal, the focus groups revealed that IPSPs prefer to retain the option of negotiating with another IPSP directly on a case-by-case basis rather than having a general policy.

The website analysis revealed that 53% of IPSP websites are available in only one language, meaning that almost half of them are translated into at least one other language.

Gender equity

Nearly 70% of IPSPs have not implemented any of the three measures for promoting gender equality that were included in the survey (i.e., using gender neutral language, creating a gender equity plan, and requiring authors to report gender-sensitive data). Meanwhile, almost 20% of IPSPs have implemented at least one of these measures, 8% have implemented two, and just 4% have implemented all three.

Among the measures that have been implemented, the most frequent is the use of gender impartial language in communications (23%), while the second-most common is a gender equity plan (GEP) (18%). With regard to GEPs, approximately 20% of IPSPs are actively developing or planning to develop one, while a comparable number say they have no such plans.

As noted above, however, the gap analysis reveals that there are discrepancies between what the IPSP claims to be doing, and what they publicly display on their website.

The focus groups reveal that, in some cases, issues of gender equity fall into the category of moral gap. Some IPSPs do not consider gender to be a quality criterion per se. Others point out the challenge of creating universal guidelines, noting that some journals in women's studies and gender studies may have women-only editorial boards (whether by design or through academic interest in the topic), and if a parity or equity standard were enforced, it could be perceived as problematic to have a women-only editorial board.

Accessibility

Of the three dimensions of interest for the DIAMAS project (i.e., multilingualism, gender equity and accessibility), accessibility is the one that has received the least attention from the IPSPs that were surveyed. Approximately two-thirds of the IPSPs have not addressed accessibility issues at all, with just 21% having a published accessibility policy and an additional 13% having an unpublished policy. The vast majority (87%) of IPSPs do not appear to meet any of the five most common accessibility standards included in the survey question (e.g. OpenAIRE guidelines, WCAG, DINI Certificate, UAAG, and ATAG), and this gap

is coupled with a considerable lack of awareness (nearly 50%) about the most common accessibility standards.

With regard to barriers, 60% of the IPSPs cite a lack of resources as being a key challenge for meeting accessibility requirements, while lack of expertise (51%) and technical limitations of infrastructure (50%) are other major barriers.

Even though this dimension of EDIB has not yet been widely addressed, the focus groups reveal that it is on the minds of the IPSPs, who express a desire to implement accessibility measures in the future, although they are not sure how to go about it since they do not have in-house expertise in this area, and may not have the necessary technologies to support it.

5.8.2 Literature

Many issues related to EDIB that were encountered in the literature have already been explored in the previous sections as they relate to the first six core components of DOAS. We will not repeat those same issues here in detail but will instead give only a brief summary and place more focus on additional issues that emerged during the literature review.

Multilingualism

Many issues surrounding multilingualism have already been discussed in relation to the first six core components of DOAS. Some additional points that were raised in the literature include the observation that very short word limits for abstracts or articles contribute to a dense writing style that can make the resulting text unnecessarily difficult to understand. Relaxing the word limit could allow authors to write a text that is more reader friendly and more translation friendly ([Steigerwald et al., 2022](#)).

Other suggestions that emerged in the literature were to provide clear guidelines to authors that would help them to cite works in other languages, as well as guidelines about how to write in a translation friendly way ([EASE, 2018](#)). Likewise, developing clear guidelines for peer reviewers that will encourage them to distinguish between content and language issues will be helpful ([Amano, Rios Rojas, et al., 2021](#)).

IPSPs should also be very clear with regard to policies about where and in what form authors can publish their work in multiple languages, integrate translation into the

workflow, and give the option of a “byline” or other recognition mechanism to credit translators for their work ([Steigerwald et al., 2022](#))

Gender equity

Many issues related to gender equity have already been discussed in relation to the first six core components of DOAS. One additional issue that emerged in the literature is that there may be a bias towards publishing research in which men are the subjects in the study (e.g. for a health issue). In an experimental study manipulating the gender of participants in a report of clinical research, ([Murrar et al., 2021](#)) found that peer reviewers were significantly more likely to recommend publishing research conducted in men than the same research conducted in women. Because women researchers are more likely than men to study women’s health ([Sugimoto et al., 2019](#)), the findings from ([Murrar et al., 2021](#)) suggest a previously unrecognized bias that could contribute to gender asymmetries in the publication outcomes of peer review, as well as gender disparities in clinical research. Explicitly adding this type of information to unconscious bias training may be a step towards reducing such bias.

Accessibility

To promote accessibility, IPSPs can include accessibility-related issues in the organization’s EDIB statement and inform themselves about the relevant legislation and compliance requirements for their region. In addition, IPSPs can develop relevant accessibility statements and policies, and they can ensure that accessibility is built into their workflow as a strategic and operational priority and not treated as an afterthought or a one-off activity ([Conrad & Kasdorf, 2018](#)).

Many aspects of accessibility are specialized, and IPSPs can support accessibility by ensuring that they know where to find appropriate expertise. IPSPs should include accessibility-related metadata for published items, and ensure that journal and ebook platforms and content are compatible with assistive technologies (e.g. screen readers). This could include presenting text in a logical reading order; ensuring that font, colour, size, and line spacing are adjustable; separating presentation and content; providing image descriptions and alt-text for pictures and captions or transcripts for videos; including page numbers; and using metadata to communicate accessibility modes and features of resources. Moreover, IPSPs can conduct regular accessibility audits ([McNaught et al., 2018](#)).

Language choices can support both accessibility and inclusion in scholarly publishing. Plain language summaries have already been mentioned; however, language intersects with EDIB in other ways also. For instance, with regard to inclusivity, using respectful language is key ([Ashwell et al., 2023](#)). Inclusive language acknowledges diversity, conveys respect to all people, is sensitive to differences, and promotes equal opportunities (e.g. [South African Journal of Science 2024](#)). When writing, it is important not to simply adopt the point of view that represents whatever group is considered to be the default group. For instance, because scholarly publishing is currently dominated by English, it can be easy to default to framing communications from a Western viewpoint ([Mertkan et al., 2017](#)). This can also apply to other groups that have traditionally held more power, such as men, White people, or able-bodied people. Looking beyond text, it is important to use inclusive images and data visualization techniques as well. IPSPs can promote inclusivity by using respectful language and diverse images on their websites and in their resources, and by adopting policies that encourage authors, peer reviewers and editors to do the same. Finally, IPSPs can provide these groups with some guidance or training resources about how to implement inclusive language and images ([Ashwell et al., 2023](#)).

Finally, ([Holt et al., 2023](#)) encourage IPSPs to capture disability data about employees and product/service users to further their EDIB goals and to accelerate diversity outcomes in scholarly publishing for both the IPSP workforce and the communities they serve.

Additional EDIB dimensions

Although this report has focused on the priority areas of EDIB identified for the DIAMAS project – namely multilingualism, gender equity, and accessible websites, content and metadata – the literature contains a wealth of information on other EDIB dimensions.

For instance, ([Else & Perkel, 2022](#)) describe a project that seeks to ask authors to disclose information about their race or ethnicity in a bid to learn more about racial bias that might occur in peer reviewing or editorial decisions. Meanwhile, ([Conroy, 2019](#)) investigates how socioeconomic status can affect scholarly publishing, ([Sverdlichenko et al., 2022](#)) look into the effects of institutional bias, while ([Kikuchi et al., 2019](#)) consider publishing barriers for early career researchers. And of course, as mentioned elsewhere, these various dimensions can intersect, creating cumulative effects for some participants in the scholarly publishing ecosystem.

6. Practical implications from scanning work

The findings from the landscape survey, gap analysis, and the literature review provide lots of food for thought. This section attempts to identify some of the practical implications arising from this work.

6.1 Multilingualism

As an increasing proportion of the scholarly publishing ecosystem becomes technologized in some way, it is important for IPSPs to carefully consider the potential impact – positive and negative – that technology can have on this field. The relationship between language and technology exemplifies the complexity and tensions that can emerge. On the one hand, some editors or IPSPs have sought to restrict the use of generative AI tools such as ChatGPT in an effort to prevent artificially generated content from being included in publications (e.g. [Thorp, 2023](#)). However, blanket policies that rule out any use of AI-based tools may unfairly penalize non-Anglophones, who could potentially use these tools for writing or editing support to reduce the cognitive and financial burdens associated with publishing in English (e.g. [Berdejo-Espinola and Amano, 2023](#)). While this type of relief is undoubtedly welcome for non-Anglophone scholars – at least as an interim step – it ultimately serves to reinforce Anglocentrism rather than supporting a genuinely multilingual publishing environment. Meanwhile, other IPSPs may try to lean too heavily on AI-based translation tools as a means of introducing multilingualism (e.g. to translate their websites) without realizing that the translation quality is very uneven across different languages, domains and purposes (e.g. reading vs writing). While translation tools may be very useful in some cases, they may be less useful (or even harmful) in others, and so decisions about the use of these tools to support scholarly publishing must be nuanced and often case by case, rather than generalized. These examples point to the fact that technology alone cannot be viewed as a solution for creating a multilingual scholarly communication ecosystem; it must be supported by appropriate policies in order to effect meaningful change.

The literature makes it clear that multilingualism is complex and challenging to implement in scholarly publishing. It may therefore be beneficial for IPSPs to take a **stepped approach** and to conceive of some **interim practices** that can improve equity in the short term, even if they do not fully or immediately realize the ultimate goal of multilingualism. For instance, as noted above, in the short term, machine translation and generative AI tools can at least reduce the cognitive and financial pressures faced by non-Anglophone scholars who are seeking to publish in English. Similarly, encouraging (and supporting) the production of

plain language summaries of research – even in English as an intermediary step – could facilitate access to knowledge by speakers of other languages since plain language will be easier to read and will more likely result in a higher quality translation when combined with an automatic translation tool.

The survey of IPSPs revealed that while publishing multilingual abstracts is relatively common, IPSPs currently put less focus on using toolkits/training to address language bias in peer review or improving machine translation literacy or translation friendly writing. In addition, more than one third have no plans to implement either machine translation or toolkits/training to address language bias. This suggests that these are gaps that DIAMAS partners could beneficially address with the planned toolkits or other measures.

As reported in D2.3 Institutional Publishing in the ERA: results from the DIAMAS survey ([Armengou et al., 2023](#)), researchers often make their decision on the publishing venues based on their perceived impact, and they use indexation or metric indicators as proxies for importance of published works. Therefore, with regard to the question of IPSPs displaying metrics for their publications, there could be a risk of creating a sort of “negative reinforcement loop” associated with displaying metrics for publications in languages other than English. If these metrics appear to be visibly lower than comparable English-language publications, then there is a risk that national or institutional research assessment systems will not endorse them and scholars will not seek to publish there.

Although the survey revealed that just 12% of IPSPs display metrics showing the geographical spread of visitors, this type of metric could be useful for identifying not only the regions of visitors, but also the associated languages, and it could thus be informative for helping and IPSP to decide whether to add a particular language to their service offering.

6.2 Gender equity

As discussed in [section 3.1.2](#) (Gender disparities), there are numerous points in the scholarly publishing process where these disparities can arise, such as in reporting on the gender of research subjects, in authorship, in the pool of peer reviewers or editorial board members, or in citation practices. While it is important to understand gender disparities in each of these individual contexts, it is also important to understand how they might interact, as well as to recognize the overall complexity of addressing gender disparity in peer review.

For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, it was observed that the overall acceptance rate for accepting peer review assignments dropped considerably; however, this decline was not spread evenly among the genders ([Squazzoni et al., 2021](#)). Indeed, the rate of acceptance by male reviewers declined, while women continued to accept peer review assignments at the pre-pandemic rate. However, during the same pandemic period, the number of manuscripts submitted by men increased, while the number submitted by women fell. This suggests that, during the pandemic, women shouldered a greater service responsibility for the journals and the community as compared to men. Meanwhile, men prioritized manuscript preparation over peer review activities. While this example pertains to a very specific set of circumstances (i.e., the COVID-19 pandemic), it points to the need for a nuanced evaluation of gender issues in scholarly publishing. In this case, increasing the proportion of women participating in peer review did not actually support a more equitable outcome overall. This is also related to questions of intersectionality (section 6.5 Intersectional disparities), since during the pandemic, women took on a disproportionate share of caregiving duties ([Collins, 2020](#); [Malisch et al., 2020](#)).

6.3 Accessible and inclusive websites, content and metadata

While there is certainly a range of general good practices that can be applied, there are also more specific regulations that differ from region to region. While the DIAMAS project is operating at a pan-European level and providing support for *general* good practices, there is also a need for localized expertise and guidance to help IPSPs achieve compliance with national and regional requirements.

Many aspects of accessibility require specialized expertise – a challenge that was identified in both the survey and the literature. In addition, accessibility compliance may be mistakenly perceived as a one-off activity, whereas in reality, it is likely to be recurrent (e.g. as websites are updated, or new content is indexed or cataloged). Together, these two factors point to a need for expertise that is **specialized** and **periodic**. Since some IPSPs (e.g. smaller organizations) may not have a sufficient volume of this type of work to warrant hiring full-time/permanent staff with the requisite skills, having access to a resource such as a database of specialists who can provide these services on a contract basis could be helpful to some IPSPs. Similarly, it is important for such organizations to be aware that they need to budget for periodic accessibility-related work rather than treating it as a one-time expense.

6.4 Intersectional disparities

Disparities may be intersectional, meaning that people who are disadvantaged in one respect may also be disadvantaged in other ways. The literature review turned up multiple examples which confirm that intersectionality exists in scholarly publishing (e.g. scholars from low-income countries may also be linguistically disadvantaged because they cannot afford professional translation or editing services; women scholars from the Global South may be doubly penalized in terms of not being cited). While there is no straightforward solution to resolve intersectionality, it is important to be aware of it. For practical reasons, IPSPs may need to prioritize certain facets of EDIB to be tackled first, just as the DIAMAS project has prioritized multilingualism, gender equity and website accessibility as initial areas of focus. However, the work cannot stop here, and there is a need to investigate other facets of EDIB in scholarly publishing, and the ways that they intersect, in the future.

6.5 Potential clashes between different sets of principles

This investigation uncovered some instances where a potential solution for improving an EDIB disparity may produce an unintended negative outcome elsewhere. For instance, there is a potential clash between a strategy that seeks to improve gender equity and a strategy aimed at promoting transparency in open scholarship. On the one hand, some IPSPs are implementing (or considering the implementation of) open reviews to promote transparency, but on the other hand, double-anonymous reviewing appears to be an effective method for combatting gender bias in peer review. Likewise, the motivated establishment of a women-only editorial board for a journal in women's studies may be undermined by a universal standard seeking to implement gender parity on all editorial boards.

Another area of potential conflict is in trying to balance the need for collecting information about gender (or race, religion or other potentially sensitive types of information) in order to monitor progress and maintain appropriate representation of various groups, and the need to respect people's right to privacy. There may be very good reasons why people do not wish to share personal details, and in some regions, there may even be regulations about what type of information can be collected.

Encouragingly, we did not uncover too many examples that point to potential clashes between different sets of principles. However, the examples that we did find underscore the need to be aware of the potential for such clashes and to carefully assess the impact

that any changes in practices or policies may bring in order to avoid a situation where addressing one issue unintentionally creates or exacerbates another problem.

7. Toolsuites and guidelines

The study of the survey, gap analysis and the literature fed directly into the creation of the toolkits and guidelines. The overview of the key players, issues, needs and gaps provided content for developing some concept maps of the field, such as the one shown for multilingualism in Figure 1.

Figure 1. An initial mind map for understanding the key players and issues with regard to multilingualism in scholarly communication.

Based on this analysis, we realized that any toolkits and guidelines developed would need to include different actors in the scholarly communication network, such as authors/researchers, peer reviewers, editors, editorial board members, librarians and IPSPs.

The literature also revealed that EDIB covers a lot of ground, leading us to the decision to create four separate toolsuite articles rather than only one. These four toolsuite articles

included an overarching toolsuite article on EDIB, as well as more focused toolsuite articles on gender equity, multilingualism, and accessible/inclusive websites, content and metadata. The various EDIB-related toolsuite articles are also cross-referenced to each other.

The literature and results of the survey and gap analysis also guided the content of the toolkits and accompanying guidelines. The goal was not to create fully original content but to identify practices, tips, and recommendations from the literature that would address the needs of IPSPs and other actors as identified in the survey and gap analysis. The issues were described in the toolsuites, and the more practical solutions for addressing them were listed in the guidelines. To create the toolsuites and guidelines, the templates provided by the DIAMAS project were used.

8. Community engagement

All toolkits and guidelines were reviewed by other members of the DIAMAS project. In addition, to engage the broader community and gather feedback on the resources that were developed, several strategies were employed: questionnaires, webinars, and blog posts and news items.

8.1 Questionnaires

Questionnaires were created to gather feedback from the wider community about both the content and the form of the toolkits and guidelines. A separate questionnaire was created for each of the three EDIB dimensions under investigation: multilingualism, gender, and accessible and inclusive websites, content and metadata. To see the questions that were included in the questionnaire on multilingualism, see [Appendix B](#). Once the questionnaires had been developed, the questions were transferred into Lime Survey, a tool for deploying online surveys and collecting responses.

8.2 Webinars

Two separate webinars were organized in collaboration with other organizations in order to promote discussion and gather feedback on the toolkits and guidelines that were developed for multilingualism, gender and accessibility.

8.2.1 Webinar on Multilingualism

The [first DIAMAS webinar on EDIB-related issues](#) focused specifically on the dimension of multilingualism. It was organized in collaboration with the [OPERAS SIG on Multilingualism](#), the [CoARA WG on Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment](#), and the [Helsinki Initiative on Multilingual Scholarly Communication](#). The webinar was organized on 28 February 2024 (15:00-16:30 CET) by DIAMAS partner TSV (Federation of Finnish Learned Societies). The [multilingualism webinar program](#) featured presentations from five speakers, followed by an open discussion:

- **Mikael Laakso**: DIAMAS project and Landscape survey on multilingualism ([synopsis and report](#))
- **Lynne Bowker**: DIAMAS Toolsuite and Guidelines on multilingualism ([presentation, toolsuite, guidelines](#))
- **Philips Ayeni**: Language technologies in scholarly publishing ([report](#))

- **Delfim Leão & Susanna Fiorini:** OPERAS translation platform ([report](#))
- **Janne Pölönen:** Helsinki Initiative and CoARA WG on Multilingualism
- **Open discussion**, including an invitation to all participants to consult the DIAMAS Toolsuite and Guidelines on Multilingualism and to offer feedback via a **survey** that was specifically prepared for this purpose (see [section 8.1](#) (Surveys)).

The webinar was advertised widely on social media (e.g., [X](#), [LinkedIn](#)). Approximately 35 people participated in the webinar, and the recording was later made available for viewing via the TSV website for people who were unable to attend live. Following the workshop, five people responded to the feedback survey and three additional people added comments directly in the guidelines documents. The comments were discussed by the DIAMAS EDIB team members and integrated into a revised version.

8.2.2 Webinar on EDIB (with a focus on gender and accessibility)

The [second DIAMAS webinar on EDIB-related issues](#) addressed the dimensions of gender and accessible and inclusive websites, content and metadata. This webinar was organized in collaboration with the [Coalition for Diversity and Inclusion in Scholarly Communication](#) (C4DISC), a group of ten trade and professional associations that represent organizations and individuals working in scholarly communications. C4DISC was formed to discuss and address issues of diversity and inclusion within this industry. The webinar was organized on 4 June (15:00-16:30 CET) by DIAMAS partners TSV and OASPA. The [gender and accessibility webinar program](#) featured presentations from three speakers, followed by an open discussion:

- **Mikael Laakso:** DIAMAS project and Landscape survey on EDIB ([presentation](#), [synopsis](#) and [report](#))
- **Lynne Bowker:** DIAMAS Toolsuite and Guidelines on EDIB ([presentation](#), [gender toolsuite](#), [gender guidelines](#), [accessibility toolsuite](#), [accessibility guidelines](#))
- **Sandra Shaw** (C4DISC Steering Committee member): C4DISC activities to promote and support EDIB ([presentation](#))
- **Janne Pölönen** (moderator).

The webinar was advertised widely on social media (e.g., [X](#), [LinkedIn](#)) and promoted by C4DISC in their networks. Approximately 70 people participated in the webinar, and the recording was later made available for viewing via the TSV website for people who were unable to attend live. Following the workshop, one completed feedback survey was

received. The comments were discussed by the DIAMAS EDIB team members and integrated into a revised version.

8.3 Blog post

To promote the EDIB-related aspects of the DIAMAS project more widely, the team prepared a blog post entitled “What can be done about scholarly communication’s diversity problem?” ([Bowker et al., 2024](#)) that was published on the LSE Impact blog on 23 May 2024. As described in the [About](#) section of their website, “The LSE Impact Blog is a hub for researchers, administrative staff, librarians, students, think tanks, government, and anyone else interested in maximising the impact of academic work in the social sciences and other disciplines.” This blog was therefore identified as a credible, high-quality venue that would reach a wide cross-section of actors involved in scholarly publishing.

To promote engagement with the community, the blog post contains links to the EDIB-related toolsuites and guidelines, and blog readers are invited to consult and offer feedback on these resources. The comment feature of the blog is active, and encouraging comments were left by a community member about the work.

When the blog post was published, various team members made additional posts to promote the piece and to drive viewers to the blog. For example, see a selection of social media posts about the blog made by various team members on [LinkedIn](#), [X](#), and [Mastodon](#).

8.4 Other activities

The DIAMAS EDIB team also participated in some other activities, including a Mutual Learning Exercise with the [OPERAS SIG on Multilingualism](#) and the [Open Access Books Network](#) (OABN) team on 27 June 2024. The DIAMAS toolkit and guidelines on Multilingualism were presented, along with a short description of the process used to create them. There was a discussion about how to put the guidelines into practice, as well as a practical session in which the OPERAS collaborative translation platform was used to try to produce drafts of parts of the guidelines in other languages.

9. Self-assessment and lessons learned

This section contains some brief comments about our experience designing and creating EDIB-related resources for the DIAMAS project:

- **Make it a collaborative process, but assign a “champion” to prepare drafts:** Meet regularly, brainstorm ideas, and record them in a shared document; however, it may be easier for one person to prepare a concrete draft and that others can respond to rather than trying to write a first draft jointly.
- **Remember the scope, but be open to learning from related areas:** This project focuses specifically on multilingualism, gender and accessible and inclusive websites, content and metadata. However, tips and recommendations that were put forward for other dimensions of EDIB were sometimes transferable to the areas of focus for our toolsuites. Considering other EDIB dimensions, at least at a high level, also provided a good reminder that there is a need to account for intersectionality.
- **Start drafting early:** There’s a lot of information out there and it would be easy to read forever. Start writing sooner rather than later. Writing concisely is very challenging and time-consuming, and multiple rounds of feedback and revisions *will* be needed.
- **Use tools to support your process:** Zotero was a huge time saver for managing references both in the library and in reference lists within documents. Working in shared documents was also a good way to encourage collaboration and feedback.
- **Sometimes less is more:** When designing the questionnaires to gather feedback, we wanted to get input on both the content and the form, but this led to the inclusion of a large number of questions. In hindsight, a slimmed down version that received more responses would have been preferable to a detailed questionnaire that generated a relatively small number of detailed responses.

10. A look to the future

When the DIAMAS project draws to a close, the work on addressing EDIB in scholarly publishing will continue. This section considers how other groups might build on the DIAMAS project results or extend EDIB-related work in the future.

While the landscape survey and gap analysis results paint a rich broad picture of what is currently happening with regard to the nature and number of EDIB dimensions that are

being addressed by the IPSPs that responded, the landscape survey does not always easily allow for the underlying reasons that motivate their decisions to be captured. Additional consultations with the community offer an opportunity to probe more deeply on some of these issues. Meanwhile, the literature raised a variety of EDIB-related issues and potential solutions, but these are sometimes idealized and may not be feasible for every IPSP to implement. Once again, the community consultations make it possible to gain a better understanding of specific conditions or constraints faced by different types of IPSPs that may facilitate or limit the approaches that they take to implementing EDIB measures. This section presents some potential questions that could be explored as part of future community consultations (e.g. focus groups).

10.1 Motivations

- **Criteria:** The IPSP landscape survey results show that a very common response for almost all of the ten EDIB dimensions surveyed was “not applicable”. This raises questions about the criteria used to make this decision. Do IPSPs interpret applicability as something that they are legally required to do, or do they simply not consider it to be of interest or importance to their stakeholders? Can DIAMAS partners encourage IPSPs to survey their own stakeholders on EDIB to get a clear measure of how important it is to their stakeholders and what the priorities should be? Can DIAMAS partners support this type of survey (e.g. by designing a survey template that IPSPs could use? By providing access to an online survey tool/platform?)
- **Incentives:** Another common response was “not planning” to implement a variety of EDIB measures, and it would be interesting to probe more deeply about the reasons why (e.g. is it a case of prioritization, or of not knowing how to begin tackling the problem?). What would incentivize IPSPs to implement additional EDIB measures?
- **Accountability:** Would some kind of low-key/low-stakes accountability or transparency help to encourage or motivate the IPSPs? Could DIAMAS partners develop a sort of “dashboard” tool that would allow IPSPs to track their own progress towards certain EDIB goals, and if desired, to make their results public (toggle between private/public)?

10.2 Priorities

- **Identify one or two priorities:** It may be challenging to tackle the implementation of all EDIB dimensions at once. Ask IPSPs to identify one (or two) EDIB-related

objectives as main priorities, and to specify particular types of support that are needed to get them to the next stage.

- **“Easy wins” and “low-hanging fruit”:** Since a high proportion of IPSPs have implemented relatively few of the EDIB dimensions, ask them to reflect on which of the EDIB strategies/solutions could be achieved with minimal effort and to address those first/next. Identifying the relatively low effort/low cost items that will provide a good and quick return on investment may help to build both momentum and experience/confidence, which could better equip the community members moving forward.
 - Alternatively, the DIAMAS partners could first attempt to organize the various strategies into categories such as “easy to implement (low effort)”, “moderately challenging to implement (moderate effort)” and “difficult to implement (major effort)” or “low cost”, “moderate cost”, and “high cost” and to present these to the community members for consideration and discussion. Of course, it may be difficult to generalize across all contexts (e.g. what is easy for a well-funded IPSP may be challenging for an IPSP with a low budget) and so the categories may need to be adapted by region, by company profile.
- Whatever the more systematic steps are after that, the key to start making progress is likely unlocked by engaging editorial boards and getting long term engagement for changes that way.

10.3 Stepped approach

- **Breaking down the problem:** EDIB is vast and complex. It could be intimidating to know how to address it. Would some kind of training or support in **planning** be useful (e.g. how to develop an EDIB strategy or an integrated action plan for EDIB?)
- **Interim solutions:** Because EDIB issues are complex, it may not be easy to jump directly to the final goal. Are there interim solutions that would advance the cause, even if they don’t fully achieve the goal? Examples: Policies allowing non-Anglophones to use AI tools to reduce the burdens of publishing in English; requesting plain language summaries in English (because they are easier for second language readers and also more translatable).

10.4 Getting started

- **Findability:** Once an IPSP decides to tackle a particular dimension of EDIB, do they already know where to find information/expertise to support their efforts? Or is not knowing where to begin or where to look for information a barrier to the efforts?

10.5 Additional resources

- **Beyond the toolsites:** Could DIAMAS partners produce other resources to assist IPSPs? For instance, would a database of accessibility experts be a useful resource? Or EDIB experts more generally? Would a collection of “samples” be helpful (e.g. sample accessibility policies, sample diversity statements)?

10.6 Format

- In cases where a lack of knowledge or lack of expertise is a barrier for implementing EDIB, which **format(s)** would be most desirable for acquiring the missing knowledge? (e.g. webinars, workshops, video resources). This information could be used to inform the development of future resources.

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Appendix A: List of some available toolkits on EDIB in scholarly publishing

This appendix contains a list of some toolkits on EDIB in scholarly publishing that are **freely available online**. The focus is on toolkits that provide practical and concrete suggestions for implementing some form of EDIB, rather than on resources that offer more general or abstract discussions about this topic. In some cases, the toolkit featured in the list is part of a larger toolkit or resource that includes information about other aspects of scholarly publishing beyond EDIB. In such cases, we have focused on the EDIB-related component but noted that it is part of a broader resource. This list is not exhaustive; rather, it seeks to present items that complement rather than repeat one another. Given that responses to EDIB issues are regularly shifting, this list prioritizes material that has been produced or updated within the past five years. The toolkits that have been selected for inclusion on this list are all available in English, but an effort has been made to highlight items that are available in other languages too.

As with any collection of information, there could be multiple possible ways of organizing the contents. In line with the mandate of this group to address multilingualism and gender diversity as priorities, the appendix is organized into the following sections: *Multilingualism*, *Gender Diversity*, *Accessibility*, and *Other*. Some of the contents in *Other* address multiple or intersectional aspects of EDIB. Another way of organizing the content could have been according to different players in the scholarly publishing system (e.g. researchers, authors, peer reviewers, editors, editorial boards, book or journal publishers, libraries). Although this particular approach was not used to organize the contents, we made an effort to ensure that each of these various groups is addressed by at least one item in the appendix.

Each entry below includes the name of the resource and the organization that has produced or shared it, along with the publication date (where available), a link to the resource, an indication of the target audience and the main focus (e.g. subcategory of EDIB addressed), and a brief summary of the contents with a particular mention of any notable or unique features. This content can later be repackaged to form the core of the DIAMAS toolkits on EDIB.

Multilingualism

Title: EASE Guidelines for Authors and Translators of Scientific Articles to be Published in English (2018)

Organization: European Association of Science Editors (EASE)

Link: <https://ease.org.uk/publications/author-guidelines-authors-and-translators/>

Target audience: Primarily authors and translators of journal articles, but also journal editors

Focus: Writing in a way that will optimize the translatability of academic articles.

Summary: Although these guidelines were initially intended to help non-Anglophones publish in English, they can serve as a general guide for writing in a translation-friendly way in any language. In other words, the guidelines can help authors to write in a way that optimizes their text for translation into another language. This can save time and effort, while also facilitating the production of a better quality translation. It can also make it easier to get good quality results from an automatic translation tool (e.g. DeepL, Google Translate).

Features:

- Link to the original open access article that introduced the guidelines: European Association of Science Editors. 2018. [EASE Guidelines for Authors and Translators of Scientific Articles to be Published in English](#). *European Science Editing* 44(4):e1-e16.
- Links to the guidelines in 30 languages.
- A short account of [how the guidelines have evolved and been implemented](#) in the decade since they were first introduced in 2009.
- Recommendation for journal editors—Consider including a statement such as the following in the journal’s Instructions to Authors: “Before submission, follow the *EASE Guidelines for Authors and Translators*, freely available in many languages at www.ease.org.uk/publications/author-guidelines. Adherence should increase the chances of acceptance of submitted manuscripts.”

Title: Running a journal in a local or regional language (2023)

Organization: Open Access Journals Toolkit

Link:

<https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/running-a-journal/running-a-journal-in-a-local-or-regional-language>

Target audience: Journal publishers

Focus: How to manage the editorial board, peer review process, website, and target audience expectations when running a journal in a local or regional language.

Summary: The Open Access Journals Toolkit has been designed to support a range of users involved in scholarly publishing with the tools needed to support a variety of regional initiatives and publishing efforts. Topics in the broader toolkit are organized into six sections, including “Running a journal”, which has a subsection related to local- or regional-language journals that could help the scholarly community achieve a state of balanced multilingualism.

Features:

- Provides a list of decision points in the form of questions that a publisher who is considering publishing a journal in a local or regional language should address.
- Contains some references to other resources on multilingualism in scholarly communication.
- Includes a version in French.

Title: Promoting Diverse, Equitable, & Inclusive Publishing Practices at the University of Florida

Organization: University of Florida, USA

Link: <https://ufl.pb.unizin.org/deipublishing/chapter/collaborate-globally/>

Target audience: Journal editors, authors, reviewers, publishers

Focus: Various aspects of EDIB, including language, gender, race and geographic origin.

Summary: In addressing EDIB, the guide references distinct concepts that encourage us to consider not only who is represented—on editorial boards and among peer reviewers,

authors, and audiences—but also what opportunities journal stakeholders have to share their perspectives and how publications’ policies, design, and outreach strategies represent these voices. In addition to covering language-related issues, the broader guide addresses other aspects of EDIB.

Features:

- Encourages journals to support multilingualism and provides some concrete suggestions for how this could be undertaken (e.g. translating websites and policies, publishing abstracts in multiple languages, providing a referral service to reputable translators/editors).
 - Offers some guidance on ways to support name (or pronoun) changes, alternative names and name disambiguation (e.g. for cultures with different naming conventions).
 - Encourages global representation and geographic diversity on editorial boards.
 - Provides examples of diversity statements to promote transparency in scholarly publishing.
 - Presents clear explanations of different models of peer review (single-anonymous review, double-anonymous review, triple-anonymous review, open review, editorial review) along with a short analysis of how each may support or hinder diversity.
-

Gender diversity

Title: Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER) Guidelines and SAGER checklist

Organization: European Association of Science Editors (EASE)

Link: <https://ease.org.uk/communities/gender-policy-committee/the-sager-guidelines/>

Target audience: Journal editors, researchers

Focus: Ensuring appropriate representation of sexes and/or genders in research subjects/study populations.

Summary: The guidelines explain the importance of sex/gender representation in study populations, particularly though not exclusively in health research, and they provide

recommendations about how the sex/gender of research subjects should be taken into account in the design of research projects and how it should be reported in various sections of a research article (e.g. title, introduction, methods, results and discussion).

Features:

- Link to the original open access article that introduced the initial SAGER guidelines: Heidari, S., Babor, T.F., De Castro, P., Tort S., Curno M. (2016) "Sex and Gender Equity in Research: rationale for the SAGER guidelines and recommended use." *Research Integrity and Peer Review* 1: 2.
 - In addition to linking to the original article with the initial guidelines in English, the EASE site also offers translations of the SAGER guidelines in six other languages (Chinese, Korean, Portuguese, Spanish, Turkish and Vietnamese).
 - To accompany the SAGER guidelines, a group of editors for *The Lancet* family of journals developed a checklist. There is a link to the original open access article that describes the implementation and checklist development: Van Epps, H., Astudillo, O., del Pozo Martín, Y., Marsh, J. (2022). "The Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER) guidelines: Implementation and checklist development." *European Science Editing* 48:e86910.
 - The Checklist is also available in Portuguese.
-

Accessibility

Title: Creating accessible content: A guide for journal editors and authors

Organization: Public Knowledge Project (PKP), Simon Fraser University, Canada

Link: <https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/accessible-content/en/>

Target audience: Journal editors and authors

Focus: Making content accessible for those with visual impairment or auditory limitations.

Summary: The Creating Accessible Content guide covers the general principles of creating universally accessible content published on the web. It highlights techniques to address specific limitations or the use of assistive technologies, such as screen readers for people

with visual impairment or sign language for those with auditory limitations. Finally, it gives specific tips on creating different galley formats in an accessible way. This guide will be useful for authors in preparation of their manuscripts and for editors in formatting materials for publication and adding content to journal websites.

Features:

- Covers general principles for creating accessible content (e.g. alt-text for images, video/audio content, accessible hyperlinks, contrast/colour reliance, readability, heading, lists, columns, tables, metadata, sign language)
- Provides guidance on creating accessible galley files (e.g. formats, labelling, document checking).
- Includes an extensive list of references to other sources.
- Available in Portuguese (<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/accessible-content/pt/>).

Title: The Inclusive Publishing Hub

Organization: The DAISY Consortium

Link: <https://inclusivepublishing.org/>

Target audience: (E)book publishers

Focus: Accessibility for people with print disabilities

Summary: On this site, which focuses on **(e)book publishing**, inclusive publishing is described as “the methodology and practice of creating a single, typically commercial publication which can be accessed by everyone irrespective of print disability, using mainstream or specialist assistive technology.” The site is maintained by the [DAISY Consortium](#), a not-for-profit global collective of organizations committed to delivering worldwide change to achieve the common vision that “People have equal access to information and knowledge regardless of disability; a right confirmed by the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.” The Consortium contributes to mainstream standards, develops guidelines to promote best practices, raises awareness of accessible reading systems and supports open standards for inclusive publishing.

Features: This site brings together links to a variety of other resources.

- Toolbox:
 - Ace Accessibility Checker
 - SMART: Simple Manual Accessibility Reporting Tool
 - DAISY Accessible Publishing Knowledge Base
 - Accessibility guidelines, standards and legislation, including:
 - EPUB Accessibility 1.0 (2017) from International Digital Publishing Forum
 - Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0 (2008) from W3C (also available in other languages)
 - Web Accessibility Initiative-Accessible Rich Internet Applications (WAI-ARIA) 1.1 from W3C
 - European Accessibility Act resources
 - Links to regional legislation for more than a dozen countries or regions.
-

Intersectional or other dimensions of EDIB beyond the scope of the DIAMAS project (e.g. race, geographic origin)

Title: Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion Toolkit for Journal Editors (2021)

Organization: American Psychological Association (APA)

Link: <https://osf.io/wst4q/> or <https://www.apa.org/pubs/authors/equity-diversity-inclusin-toolkit-journal-editors.pdf>

Target audience: Journal editors

Focus: Racial equity

Summary: APA seeks to encourage its members to increase the diversity of research samples, engage with communities of color in planning, conducting, interpreting, and communicating research, and ensure that scholars of color are represented on peer review panels and editorial boards, among other actions. This toolkit offers guidance for acting on these and other strategies for dismantling systemic racism in psychology research and publishing. Specifically, this toolkit offers more than 30 recommended actions that journal editors can take to promote EDIB – explicitly with regard to race – in their journals.

Features:

- Selecting methods for promoting inclusivity and diversity in a journal (e.g. publishing a diversity statement, adding EDIB terms to keywords or classification terms)
 - Adopting inclusive reporting standards for authors
 - Applying mechanisms for reporting equity through open science
 - Improving editorial board representation
 - Implementing inclusive peer review
 - Using bias-free language
 - Implementing an EDIB checklist for journal editors
-

Title: Diversifying editorial boards (2021)

Organization: Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)

Link: <https://publicationethics.org/news/diversifying-editorial-boards>

Target audience: Journal editors, publishers

Focus: Diversifying editorial boards in numerous ways (e.g. by career stage, gender, geographical origin, race)

Summary: A collection of practical suggestions from the COPE community about diversifying editorial boards as an initial step towards future work on improving EDIB in scholarly publishing.

Features:

- Lists concrete ways in which editors/publishers can seek to diversify editorial boards (e.g. set targets, appoint champions, set fixed terms, post open calls, take unconscious bias training).
 - Provides links to related resources.
-

Title: Open reviewers bias reflection guide (2021)

Organization: PREreview

Link: <https://zenodo.org/records/5484052>

Target audience: Reviewers

Focus: Guiding reviewers in a self-reflection exercise to consider their own unconscious bias as it may reflect gender, race, country of origin, institutional affiliation, career stage, language, etc.

Summary: PREreview’s mission is to bring more equity and transparency to scholarly peer review by supporting and empowering communities of researchers, particularly those at early stages of their career (ECRs) and historically excluded, to review preprints in a process that is rewarding to them. The Bias Reflection Guide is a tool developed by the PREreview team for anyone who is reviewing a research manuscript before or after the manuscript publication. The tool is meant to help the reviewer assess their own biases guiding them through a non-judgmental, self-reflective process.

Features:

- Includes a list of questions for self-reflection, as well as a method to help reviewers identify, evaluate and address their biases and assumptions.
- Links to two other guides that are also part of the PREreview Open Reviewers toolkit: the [Reviewer Guide](#) and the [Review Assessment Rubric](#).

Title: Diversity, equity and inclusion in scholarly communication—Libraries (2023)

Organization: Office of Scholarly Communication, University of California, USA

Link:

<https://osc.universityofcalifornia.edu/scholarly-publishing/diversity-equity-and-inclusion-in-scholarly-communication/libraries/>

Target audience: Academic library workers

Focus: Addresses various types of equity that cover race, language/culture, geographic origin, and learning styles.

Summary: Provides suggestions for how academic library workers can integrate EDIB into the various roles that they play within the scholarly communication lifecycle (e.g. content selection, discoverability of content, support for researchers).

Features:

- Points to additional resources for integrating EDIB into library activities.
 - The parent site also includes suggestions for other players in the scholarly community (e.g. peer reviewers, editorial boards, authors, publishers).
-

Title: Guidelines on inclusive language and images in scholarly communication (October 2022)

Organization: Coalition for Diversity and Inclusion in Scholarly Communication (C4DISC)

Link:

<https://c4disc.pubpub.org/guidelines-on-inclusive-language-and-images-in-scholarly-communication>

Target audience: Authors, editors, and reviewers

Focus: Inclusive and culturally sensitive language and images

Summary: The purpose of these guidelines is to help all authors, editors, and reviewers recognize the use of language and images that are inclusive and culturally sensitive. The guidelines will serve as a global tool and educational resource that can be used by individuals, institutions, and publishers. By addressing the various forms of bias and discrimination currently found in published research, the intent of these guidelines is to set an industry standard that promotes proactive inclusive communication going forward. These guidelines are part of a larger C4DISC project to create a series of Toolkits for Equity.

Features:

- Provides suggestions for how to select inclusive terms (e.g. person-first language) or to apply inclusive language (e.g. to avoid misgendering or Eurocentric framing).
 - Points to resources that contain a wide selection diverse images.
-

Title: A Focused Toolkit for Journal Editors and Publishers: Building Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility in Editorial Roles and Peer Review

Organization: Coalition for Diversity and Inclusion in Scholarly Communication (C4DISC)

Link: <https://doi.org/10.21428/77410d6b.91056a07>

Target audience: Editors, publishers

Focus: Building Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility in Editorial Roles and Peer Review

Summary: The toolkit is focused nurturing diversity among peer reviewers and fostering equity in the actions of peer reviewers. It further provides guidance on how EDIB can be integrated into the core actions of editors and publishers.

Features:

- A toolkit organised around 5 core recommendations: 1. Develop an Inclusive Culture and Mission, 2. Collect and Report Demographic Data, 3. Recruit Broadly and Intentionally, 4. Train and Mentor Reviewers, 5. Foster Equity in Peer Review
- Provides very actionable steps, but also integrated with rich linking to academic sources as well as industry reports
- Custom-painted thematic art for each section, providing a visually stimulating toolkit.

Title: Author diversity report and toolkit (2021)

Organization: Publishers Association (UK)

Link: <https://www.publishers.org.uk/publications/author-diversity-report-and-toolkit/>

Target audience: Book publishers (fiction and non-fiction)

Focus: Racial equity

Summary: A toolkit intended to provide advice and guidance on best practice for gathering author data relating to protected characteristics (e.g. ethnic origin, gender, sexual

orientation, socio-economic status) as a step towards achieving a more diverse representation of authors.

Features:

- Supplies a template for an 18-question survey that publishers can use to conduct an author diversity audit within their own organization.
- Contains guidance on complying with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- Provides recommendations relating to the timing and deployment of the survey (e.g. suggests tools/platforms that could be used to host or distribute the survey).
- Includes links to EDIB policies and activities at many UK publishers.

Appendix B: Questionnaires used to gather feedback on toolsuites and guidelines as part of community engagement activities

Note: The questions in this appendix pertain to the Multilingualism toolsuite and guidelines, but comparable questionnaires were created and deployed to gather feedback on the toolsuites and guidelines for Gender and the Accessibility. The questions were transferred into the Lime Survey tool for easy online deployment (by sharing a link) and data collection.

PLEASE SHARE YOUR FEEDBACK ON THE DIAMAS MULTILINGUALISM TOOLSUITE AND GUIDELINES

Thank you for attending the DIAMAS webinar on Multilingualism (28 February 2024). As you learned, we have developed a preliminary toolsuite on Multilingualism, as well as an accompanying set of guidelines. We would really value your feedback on these preliminary versions so that we may revise and improve them before sharing them more widely.

This survey will take no more than 10 minutes to complete, and it does not require you to enter any personal information.

You can consult the [Multilingualism Toolsuite](#) and the [Multilingualism Guidelines](#) to refresh your memory about their contents.

MULTILINGUALISM TOOLSUITE

Q1: Overall, the toolsuite is reasonably complete.

Disagree
Somewhat disagree
Somewhat agree
Agree

Q2: Do you have any specific recommendations for additional information that should be included in the toolsuite?

Q3: Overall, the toolsuite is well organized and it is easy to find information.

- Disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Somewhat agree
- Agree

Q4: Do you have any recommendations for reorganizing the content in the toolsuite?

Q5: Overall, the toolsuite is well written (clear, unambiguous, easy to read).

- Disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Somewhat agree
- Agree

Q6: Do you have any specific suggestions for improving the linguistic quality of the toolsuite?

Q7: Overall, the list of references in the toolsuite seem relevant and helpful.

- Disagree
- Somewhat disagree

Somewhat agree

Agree

Q8: Do you have any specific suggestions for references that you would like to see added to the toolsuite?

Q9: Overall, the list of additional resources provided in the toolsuite seem relevant and helpful.

Disagree

Somewhat disagree

Somewhat agree

Agree

Q10: Do you have any specific suggestions for additional resources that you would like to see added to the toolsuite?

Q11: Do you have any other comments that you would like to share about the toolsuite?

MULTILINGUALISM GUIDELINES

Q12: Overall, the division of guidelines into the categories A) Easy to accomplish, B) Moderate investments for the mid-term, and C) Longer term goals, is relevant and useful.

Disagree

Somewhat disagree
Somewhat agree
Agree

Q13: Do you have any specific suggestions for adding, removing or renaming the three categories?

Q14: Overall, the items listed in Section A are indeed relatively easy to accomplish and should remain in this category.

Disagree
Somewhat disagree
Somewhat agree
Agree

Q15: Do you have specific suggestions for missing items that you think should be included in section A?

Q16: Do you have specific suggestions for items in section A that you think should be relocated to section B or section C, or deleted from the guidelines altogether? (please specify)

Q17: Do you think that any of the items in section A should be reordered (i.e., moved up or down the list with regard to priority or importance)? (please specify)

Q18: Overall, the items listed in Section B are indeed items that represent moderate investments for the mid-term and should remain in this category.

- Disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Somewhat agree
- Agree

Q19: Do you have specific suggestions for missing items that you think should be included in section B?

Q20: Do you have specific suggestions for items in section B that you think should be relocated to section A or section C, or deleted from the guidelines altogether? (please specify)

Q21: Do you think that any of the items in section B should be reordered (i.e., moved up or down the list with regard to priority or importance)? (please specify)

Q22: Overall, the items listed in Section C are indeed relatively easy to accomplish and should remain in this category.

- Disagree

Somewhat disagree
Somewhat agree
Agree

Q23: Do you have specific suggestions for missing items that you think should be included in section C?

Q24: Do you have specific suggestions for items in section C that you think should be relocated to section A or section B, or deleted from the guidelines altogether? (please specify)

Q25: Do you think that any of the items in section C should be reordered (i.e., moved up or down the list with regard to priority or importance)? (please specify)

Q26: Overall, the guidelines are well written (clear, unambiguous, easy to read).

Disagree
Somewhat disagree
Somewhat agree
Agree

Q27: Do you have any specific suggestions for improving the linguistic quality of the guidelines?

Q28: Overall, the list of further reading provided in the guidelines seems relevant and helpful.

- Disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Somewhat agree
- Agree

Q29: Do you have any specific suggestions for further reading that you would like to see added to the guidelines?

Q30: Do you have any other comments that you would like to share about the guidelines?

Thank you very much for taking the time to provide feedback on the DIAMAS Multilingualism toolsuite and guidelines. Your input will help us to improve these resources!

